

ENTREPRENEDEU

Enhancing entrepreneurial ecosystems for education

**ELABORATION AND DELIVERY OF THE MENTORING
MODULES**

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D4.2 ELABORATION AND DELIVERY OF THE MENTORING MODULES

MENTORING PROGRAMME REPORT

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ABSTRACT	THIS REPORT PROVIDES AN OVERVIEW OF THE ENTREPRENEDU MENTORING PROGRAMME'S FIRST INITIATION, DETAILING ITS CREATION, STRUCTURE, EXECUTION, AND RESULTS. IT INCLUDES FEEDBACK COLLECTED FROM PARTICIPANTS TO ENHANCE FUTURE ITERATIONS AND OUTLINES ONGOING MENTORING PROCESSES FOR COHORT 2. THE PROGRAMME, FEATURING SIX MODULES BLENDING E-LEARNING AND INTERACTIVE MENTORSHIP, DEMONSTRATED HIGH PARTICIPANT SATISFACTION, WITH AREAS FOR IMPROVEMENT IDENTIFIED AND ADDRESSED. COHORT 2, FOLLOWING A SIMILAR STRUCTURE WITH ADJUSTMENTS INFORMED BY

	FEEDBACK, IS CURRENTLY UNDERWAY.
KEYWORDS	MENTORING, PLATFORM, PROGRAMME, FEEDBACK, COHORT

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report outlines the creation, structure, execution and results of the first initiation of the ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring Programme. Further, it entails and derived actions of a feedback collection from participants of the first ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring Programme Cohort. Moreover, a short overview of the ongoing mentoring process for Cohort 2 is provided

The mentoring programme has been carefully structured into six modules, providing a comprehensive journey from ideation to execution for the entrepreneurial teams. We have integrated a blend of e-learning with interactive mentorship to offer a dynamic, tailored learning experience. The programme's implementation took place during the Kick-Off Meeting on the 17th of October 2023.

The execution of the programme followed three distinct phases. In the first phase, the mentees were provided with three training videos for each module and had the opportunity to test their understanding of the content in quizzes. In the second phase, an online workshop, Q&A session and individual mentoring sessions were provided to the mentees. Lastly, in the third phase, a reflection session was held in all modules with the mentees. The structure, goal, content and results for each of these phases are provided in this report for all mentoring modules.

During the reflection session, Fraunhofer IPK collected the feedback from the mentees to derive measures to improve the programme. The feedback collection covered the following topics: Reflection on the Mentoring Journey, Overcoming Obstacles and Developing Skills, Business Model Evaluation, Progress and Future Goals, Learning from the Community, Overall Satisfaction with the Mentoring Program and Modules and Technical, Organisational Feedback and Closing thoughts. Across all mentoring modules, the participants indicate a high level of satisfaction. However, some measures were derived to improve the mentoring experience for future cohorts. These measures include: Develop clearer guidelines on the sequence and interplay of different module, Tailor Modules to the participants' readiness level, Implement a streamlined unified scheduling process, Expand the curriculum to include modules on HR Management and Leadership, explore opportunities to enhance user interaction and ease of accessing materials on the mentoring platform.

The second Cohort, consisting of four teams from the Greek Hackathon and one team from the previous Hackathon in Rimini, Italy, convened for its Kick-off meeting on January 23, 2024. Scheduled from January to April 2024, the mentoring program for Cohort 2 closely follows the structure of the first cohort, with adjustments made based on the feedback. Live sessions have been emphasized, and are now all facilitated through Google Meets for consistency, with phase 1 completed and phase 2 underway.

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1 INTRODUCTION OF THE MENTORING PROGRAMME REPORT

This section introduces the ENTREPRENEDU Project and its objectives. Further, the structure and the purpose of this report are highlighted.

The concept of ENTREPRENEDU is focused on closing the innovation and educational gap between different regions of the EU. One important tool to do so is the creation of a highly replicable and scalable Venture Building Program, an educational model for the European entrepreneurial ecosystems that will be validated at the end of the project in 3 different educational entities.

The foundation for the Venture Building Program will be laid by a mentoring program that takes in the 12 teams and start-ups selected during three Hackathons in low to medium innovation countries of Greece, Italy and Bulgaria. At each Hackathon, different teams and start-ups compete to deliver solutions for pressing issues in the European Union. The four most promising ideas at each Hackathon will be selected and take part in the ENTREPRENEDU mentoring program as a cohort.

This report aims to highlight the structure and implementation of the ENTREPRENEDU mentoring programme. Further, it is reported on the mentoring activities and the mentee participation in detail. Additionally, feedback from mentees and mentors is processed and actions for improvement are derived. The report fully covers the first execution of the mentoring programme (Cohort 1) and partially covers the second execution of the mentoring programme (Cohort 2). This report is structured as follows: Subsequently to this introduction, chapter 2 provides an overview of the structure of the mentoring programme. Chapter 3 describes how the mentoring programme was executed. In chapter 4, an overview of the mentoring activities and results of cohort 1 is provided. Further, the feedback of the mentees and mentors is discussed and suggestions for improvement are provided. Chapter 5 illustrates the outlook for cohort 2. Lastly, chapter 6 concludes this report

2 STRUCTURE OF THE MENTORING PROGRAMME

This section describes the nature and overall structure of the mentoring programme and discusses its distinct phases. The programme follows a blended learning approach that combines live mentoring and interaction with E-Learning to create a transformative educational journey for its participants.

Figure 1 illustrates the various stages, depth of learning, and content framework of the mentoring program. This structure was crafted based on insights derived from a demand analysis which was executed with the mentees of cohort 1. Findings revealed that teams and startups are dispersed across different regions in Italy, with varying levels of expertise. As a result, a blended learning approach allows participants to engage from their respective locations and accommodate their diverse skill sets.

The initial phase, characterized by systematic preparation, involves standardized content delivery aimed at imparting fundamental knowledge through online mediums such as webinars and training videos. This content remains consistent across all participants in the inaugural cohort and includes rudimentary assessment measures, potentially in the form of quizzes.

Moving to the second phase, emphasis shifts towards tailored development, offering more advanced learning opportunities that cater to individual needs. This stage unfolds in a live mentoring environment, fostering interaction between mentors and participants. Workshops, Q&A sessions, and one-on-one mentorship are all viable formats during this phase.

Lastly, the closing phase centers on reflection and feedback. Participants connect with their mentor for a final evaluation of their progress, development, and goal achievements.

FIGURE 1: Blended Learning Structure

Table 1 offers a detailed overview of the mentoring program's three distinct phases, outlining their respective mentoring units, components, objectives, as well as the duration and planned implementation dates. Phase one kicked off in October 2023, marking the program's initiation. It spans four hours, providing participants with essential guidance and support to establish a robust foundation for their entrepreneurial endeavors.

Phase two, spanning from October 2023 to February 2024, constitutes the most extensive segment of the mentoring program. Participants will engage in five hours of mentoring, aimed at delving deeper into various aspects of their startup ventures, fostering comprehensive skill development and knowledge enhancement.

The final phase, slated for March 2024, encompasses a one-hour mentoring reflection session, representing the shortest duration among the three phases. In total, the mentoring program will offer ten hours of valuable mentorship to each participant, aiming to maximize the potential of the first cohort of teams and startups and contribute to their long-term success.

Considering the involvement of six mentoring organizations, each startup within the first cohort is poised to benefit from a total of 60 hours of mentoring.

TABLE 1: Detailed view of the mentoring programme structure

Phase	Mentoring Unit	Mentoring Element	Mentoring Objective	Duration	Dates (for Cohort 1)
Phase 1: Methodical preparation	Webinar / Training-Videos	Three consecutive webinar / training videos (Level 1-3)	Teaching the methodological basis	3h (1h each)	October 2023
	Learning success control	Quiz via online tool	Reflection and deepening of the acquired knowledge	1h	
Phase 2: Development phase	Workshop with guided Exercises (small group)	Interactive Workshop e.g. with whiteboard	Guided Peer learning (start-ups give each other feedback)	2h	October 2023 – February 2024
	Meet-the-Mentor / Q&A Session (small group)	Live session (small group)	Clarification of questions from the guided exercise	1h	
	Individual Mentoring Session	Live session (One-to-One)	Mentor supports identification of obstacles and in developing strategies to overcome them.	2h (2 Sessions à 1h)	
Phase 3: Closing phase	Reflection session (individual)	Live session (One-to-One)	Reflection on the development and progress of the mentee and the achievement of the goals.	1h	March 2024
				Total: 10h	

3 EXECUTION OF MENTORING PROGRAMME

This section outlines the implementation of Cohort 1's mentoring program, detailing the execution process of its various phases.

Based on a demand analysis, which was conducted with the participating mentees the following mentoring modules have been defined for the mentoring programme:

Mentoring Module 1: Business Model Development (Expert: Fraunhofer IPK)

- Mentoring Module 2: Crafting a Unique and Competitive Value Proposition (Expert: LUISS)
- Mentoring Module 3: Your Idea Pitch: from Tech Feasibility to Product Development (Expert: FEA)
- Mentoring Module 4: Investment Pitch and Quantifying Your Funding Needs (Expert: EBAN)
- Mentoring Module 5: Entrepreneurial Business Planning (Expert: Corallia)
- Mentoring Module 6: Access to Finance and Related Funding (Expert: Cleantech Bulgaria)

The mentoring program for Cohort 1 commenced on October 17, 2023, with a two-hour session attended by all mentors and representatives of the mentored teams. During this session, the mentoring program was thoroughly explained, and each mentor provided an overview of their specific mentoring module's

structure, goals, and requirements. Additionally, mentees were given the opportunity to ask questions and address any pressing issues. A Screenshot of the event is provided below.

FIGURE 2: Screenshot of the Kick-Off Meeting

Subsequently, Cohort 1 participants registered their startups on the F6S platform to access the dedicated mentoring pages per module. These pages served as hubs for sharing links to training videos and quizzes, as well as enabling mentors to post announcements and communicate with mentees. Further, a description of the overall module was highlighted on each individual mentoring page. The F6S platform also hosted the quiz formulas used by mentees to assess their understanding of the mentoring modules. Workshops, Q&A sessions, individual mentorship, and reflection sessions were conducted by mentors using their preferred online meeting tool. The coordination of these sessions was primarily facilitated by Fraunhofer IPK.

4 COHORT 1

This section will provide detailed descriptions of various mentoring modules, focusing on the phases within each module. This will include discussions on training videos, quizzes, workshops, Q&A sessions, individual mentorship, and reflection sessions. The illustration will follow a logical sequence. Firstly, the structure of each mentoring element will be described. Secondly, the overarching goals of these elements will be explained. Thirdly, the actual mentoring content provided will be illustrated. Finally, the outcomes

of the mentoring elements and the participation of the mentees will be described. The detailed time-schedule for the mentoring is provided in the Appendix.

4.1 FRAUNHOFER IPK – BUSINESS MODEL DEVELOPMENT

TRAINING VIDEOS

STRUCTURE

THE TRAINING VIDEOS SERVE AS THE INITIAL MENTORING ELEMENT, WITH EACH OF THE THREE VIDEOS LASTING ABOUT ONE HOUR A TOTAL OF APPROXIMATELY THREE HOURS OF VIDEO MATERIAL IS PROVIDED. THE MENTORS PRE-RECORD THE VIDEOS WHICH ARE THEN LINKED TO ON THE F6S PLATFORM.

GOAL

THE TRAINING VIDEOS AIM TO INTRODUCE THE MENTEES INTO THE TOPIC OF THE MODULE AND PROVIDE THEM WITH A BASIC UNDERSTANDING OF THE ESSENTIAL COMPONENTS OF THE MODULE. THE FIRST VIDEO SERVES AS AN INTRODUCTORY SESSION TO THE TOPIC OF THE MENTORING MODULE. THE SECOND VIDEO DELVES DEEPER INTO THE MODULE'S TOPICS, WHILE THE FINAL VIDEO FOCUSES ON THE MOST COMPLEX ASPECTS COVERED IN THE MENTORING MODULE.

VIDEO 1: IN THE VIDEO, A FUNDAMENTAL UNDERSTANDING OF BUSINESS MODEL DEVELOPMENT IS PROVIDED. IT IS EXPLAINED THAT IT'S NOT JUST ABOUT UNDERSTANDING ONE'S PRODUCT OR SERVICE, BUT ALSO ABOUT UNDERSTANDING THE ECOSYSTEM IN WHICH THE FUTURE BUSINESS OPERATES. THE CHALLENGES FACED BY BUDDING ENTREPRENEURS AND THE IMPORTANCE OF FEEDBACK AND MENTORSHIP IN DEFINING A ROBUST BUSINESS MODEL ARE HIGHLIGHTED. BY THE END OF THE VIDEO, VIEWERS ARE SAID TO BE EQUIPPED WITH THE KNOWLEDGE TO START, REDEFINE, OR PIVOT THEIR CURRENT OR FUTURE BUSINESS MODEL TO BETTER ALIGN WITH THEIR BUSINESS GOALS.

FIGURE 3: Screenshot of the first training video by Fraunhofer IPK

CONTENT

VIDEO 2: THE VIDEO PROVIDES A DETAILED EXPLANATION OF THE BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS (BMC), AIMING TO OFFER AN ADVANCED UNDERSTANDING OF ITS ELEMENTS AND APPLICATION AS A TOOL. IT COVERS THE DEFINITION AND HISTORY OF THE BMC, INTRODUCES VARIOUS ADAPTATIONS, DISCUSSES ITS ELEMENTS IN DETAIL, AND PROVIDES EXAMPLES OF BMC APPLICATIONS

FIGURE 4: Screenshot of the second training video by Fraunhofer IPK

VIDEO 3: IN THE VIDEO, AN OVERVIEW IS GIVEN OF AN APPROACH TO CONTINUOUSLY ADAPT, DEVELOP, AND CHANGE A BUSINESS MODEL ACCORDING TO EXTERNAL AND INTERNAL DRIVERS. FOR THIS PURPOSE, A FRAMEWORK FOR STRATEGIC BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT IS INTRODUCED AND FILLED WITH PRACTICAL TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES TO ANALYZE INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL FACTORS AFFECTING THE BUSINESS MODEL, AS WELL AS TO DERIVE RELEVANT ACTIONS TO SYSTEMATICALLY DEVELOP THE BUSINESS MODEL IN ORDER TO GROW AND SURVIVE AS A SUCCESSFUL COMPANY ON THE MARKET.

FIGURE 4: Screenshot of the third training video by Fraunhofer IPK

ALL THREE TRAINING VIDEOS HAVE BEEN PROVIDED BY THE MENTORING ORGANIZATION AND HAVE BEEN CONSUMED BY THE MENTEES.

RESULTS

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 3H

QUIZ

STRUCTURE

ON THE F6S PLATFORM A MULTIPLE-CHOICE QUIZ WAS IMPLEMENTED FOR EVERY MENTORING MODULE. THE AMOUNT OF QUESTIONS RANGED BETWEEN 24 AND 30. THE QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE THREE MENTORING VIDEOS. IT WAS ESTIMATED THAT THE COMPLETION OF ONE QUIZ TAKES ONE HOUR.

GOAL

THE QUIZ IS NON-MANDATORY BUT AIMS TO TEST THE MENTEES UNDERSTANDING OF MENTORING VIDEOS TO THEN FOCUS IN THE FOLLOWING MENTORING PROCESS ON AREAS WHERE THE PERFORMANCE IN THE QUIZ WAS LACKING.

CONTENT

THE QUIZ INCLUDES BOTH THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE CONTENT PRESENTED IN THE 3 VIDEOS OF THE MODULE. THE QUESTIONS ARE FORMED IN A WAY THAT MAKES IT EASY TO VERIFY WHETHER THE MENTEES HAVE INDEED WATCHED THE VIDEOS, AND TO IDENTIFY SPECIFIC AREAS ON WHICH THE TEAMS MAY NEED EXTRA CLARIFICATIONS.

RESULTS

UNFORTUNATELY, NONE OF THE TEAMS COMPLETED THE QUIZ.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

WORKSHOP

STRUCTURE

THE WORKSHOP SESSION IS THE FIRST LIVE INTERACTION OF THE MENTOR AND THE MENTEES. THE SESSION IS HELD ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THE WORKSHOP SESSION HAS A DURATION OF 2 HOURS AND IS OPEN FOR ALL MENTEES.

GOAL

IN THE WORKSHOP, THE DIFFERENT MENTEES CAN APPLY THE THEORETICAL CONCEPTS LEARNED IN THE TRAINING VIDEOS TO THEIR OWN BUSINESS ENDEAVOR.

IN THIS SESSION, THE WHITEBOARD TOOL "CONCEPTBOARD" WAS USED TO LET THE MENTEES FILL OUT THEIR OWN BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS (BMC). EACH TEAM HAD THEIR INDIVIDUAL VIRTUAL ROOM IN WHICH THE MENTORS PROVIDED SUPPORT. LATER ON, THE TEAMS PRESENTED THEIR STATUS OF THE BMC AND RECEIVED FEEDBACK FROM THE MENTORS AND THEIR PEERS.

FIGURE 5: Screenshot of the Results of the BMC Workshop

CONTENT

RESULTS

ALL FOUR TEAMS PARTICIPATED IN THE WORKSHOP AND FILLED OUT THEIR BMC.

THE WORKSHOP HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON 01/12/2023.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H

Q&A SESSION

STRUCTURE	THE Q&A SESSION WAS FACILITATED ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THE DURATION OF THE SESSION WAS 1 HOUR AND OPEN FOR ALL MENTEES TO ENTER AND ASK QUESTIONS ABOUT MENTORING RELATED TOPICS.
GOAL	THE Q&A SESSION AIMS TO PROVIDE THE MENTEES WITH AN OPPORTUNITY TO ASK QUESTIONS AND TO SOLVE DOUBTS RAISED FROM THE PREVIOUS TRAINING VIDEOS AND WORKSHOP.
CONTENT	DURING THE SESSION A PARTICULAR FOCUS WAS PUT ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE BMC OF THE START-UPS. THE MENTORS PROVIDED SUGGESTIONS ON HOW TO OVERCOME SPECIFIC CHALLENGES. ALL MENTEES RECEIVED GUIDANCE TAILORED TO THEIR UNIQUE NEEDS. ALL FOUR TEAMS ACTIVELY ENGAGED IN THE Q&A SESSION AND ASKED QUESTIONS.
RESULTS	THE SESSION HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON 04/12/2024. TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS

STRUCTURE	TWO INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS FOR EACH START-UP, EACH WITH A DURATION OF ONE HOUR, WERE OFFERED ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR, LEADING TO A TOTAL OF TWO HOURS OF MENTORING PER START-UP. IN THESE SESSIONS ONLY, THE MENTORS AND ONE START-UP ARE PRESENT TO FOCUS ON THEIR SPECIFIC NEEDS AND ISSUES.
GOAL	THE INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS PROVIDE PERSONALIZED GUIDANCE TO EACH START-UP, HELPING THEM OVERCOME SPECIFIC OBSTACLES ENCOUNTERED DURING CRITICAL PHASES OF THEIR COMPANIES. THIS ASSISTANCE AIDS IN DEVELOPING EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR THE FUTURE.
CONTENT	IN THE INDIVIDUAL SESSION THE BMC OF THE START-UPS WAS REVIEWED AND COMPLETED. THE SESSIONS BEGAN WITH A THOROUGH REVIEW OF THE STARTUP'S CURRENT BMC. MENTORS AND MENTEES COLLABORATIVELY EXAMINED EACH COMPONENT OF THE CANVAS, FROM THE VALUE PROPOSITION TO CUSTOMER SEGMENTS, CHANNELS, REVENUE STREAMS, AND KEY ACTIVITIES. FURTHER, THE FOCUS WAS PLACED ON PROVIDING AND DISCUSSING FITTING BUSINESS MODEL PARTNERS THAT THE START-UP CAN APPLY TO THEIR BMC. WHERE GAPS WERE IDENTIFIED, MENTORS PROVIDED TARGETED ADVICE ON HOW TO ADDRESS THEM, ENSURING THAT BY THE END OF THE SESSION, EACH STARTUP HAD A COMPLETED BMC THAT WAS BOTH REALISTIC AND AMBITIOUS. A SIGNIFICANT PORTION OF THESE SESSIONS WAS DEDICATED TO EXPLORING AND SELECTING FITTING BUSINESS MODEL PATTERNS THAT STARTUPS COULD INTEGRATE INTO THEIR BMC. THIS EXPLORATION WAS GUIDED BY THE MENTOR'S EXPERTISE IN IDENTIFYING PATTERNS THAT HAVE PROVEN SUCCESSFUL ACROSS VARIOUS INDUSTRIES AND HOW THEY COULD BE TAILORED TO THE TEAMS' SPECIFIC CONTEXT. DISCUSSIONS REVOLVED AROUND A RANGE OF INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODEL PATTERNS.

FIGURE 6: Screenshot of the Results of the Individual Sessions by Fraunhofer IPK

RESULTS

THE START-UP A COMMUNICATED THAT THEY HAD ISSUES TO ATTEND THE MENTORING SESSIONS. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION BUT UNFORTUNATELY DID NOT GET A RESPONSE. HENCE, THE START-UP A DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

THE START-UP B PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS AND FINALIZED ITS BMC (08/01/2024 & 22/01/2024). FURTHER, FITTING BUSINESS MODEL PATTERNS TO APPLY TO THE START-UPS BUSINESS MODEL WERE DISCUSSED.

THE START-UP C PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (16/01/2024 & 24/01/2024). AND FINALIZED ITS BMC. FURTHER, FITTING BUSINESS MODEL PATTERNS TO APPLY TO THE START-UPS BUSINESS MODEL WERE DISCUSSED.

THE START-UP D PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (15/01/2024 & 01/02/2024) AND FINALIZED ITS BMC. FURTHER, FITTING BUSINESS MODEL PATTERNS TO APPLY TO THE START-UPS BUSINESS MODEL WERE DISCUSSED.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H

REFLECTION SESSIONS

STRUCTURE	A ONE-HOUR REFLECTION SESSION WAS OFFERED TO ALL MENTEES ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THIS SESSION FOCUSED ON PROVIDING FEEDBACK TO THE MENTEES AND MARKED THE END OF THIS MENTORING MODULE
GOAL	THE REFLECTION SESSION AIMS TO ENCOURAGE PARTICIPANTS TO PRACTICE SELF-ASSESSMENT AND REFLECTION, ENABLING THEM TO MONITOR THEIR PROGRESS, ACKNOWLEDGE THEIR ACHIEVEMENTS, AND IDENTIFY AREAS FOR FUTURE DEVELOPMENT.
CONTENT	IN THE REFLECTION SESSION, A GUIDED DISCUSSION BETWEEN THE MENTOR AND THE MENTEE TOOK PLACE. THE FOCUS WAS PUT ON REVIEWING THE BMC AND DEVELOPING ACTIONS TO IMPROVE THE START-UP IN THE FUTURE. THE START-UP B PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON 12/02/2024 AND THE OVERALL PROCESS OF THE BMC DEVELOPMENT WAS REVIEWED. FURTHER, THE OVERALL MENTORING PROCESS OF THE MODULE AND PROGRAMME WAS DISCUSSED AND FEEDBACK COLLECTED.
RESULTS	THE START-UP C PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON 14/02/2024 AND THE AND THE OVERALL PROCESS OF THE BMC DEVELOPMENT WAS REVIEWED. FURTHER, THE OVERALL MENTORING PROCESS OF THE MODULE AND PROGRAMME WAS DISCUSSED AND FEEDBACK COLLECTED. THE START-UP D PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON 16/02/2024 AND THE AND THE OVERALL PROCESS OF THE BMC DEVELOPMENT WAS REVIEWED. FURTHER, THE OVERALL MENTORING PROCESS OF THE MODULE AND PROGRAMME WAS DISCUSSED AND FEEDBACK COLLECTED.
	TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

4.2 LUISS - CRAFTING A UNIQUE AND COMPETITIVE VALUE PROPOSITION

TRAINING VIDEOS

STRUCTURE	THE TRAINING VIDEOS SERVE AS THE INITIAL MENTORING ELEMENT, WITH EACH OF THE THREE VIDEOS LASTING ABOUT ONE HOUR, A TOTAL OF APPROXIMATELY THREE HOURS OF VIDEO MATERIAL IS PROVIDED. THE MENTORS PRE-RECORD THE VIDEOS, WHICH ARE THEN LINKED TO ON THE F6S PLATFORM
GOAL	THE TRAINING VIDEOS AIM TO INTRODUCE THE MENTEES INTO THE TOPIC OF THE MODULE AND PROVIDE THEM WITH A BASIC UNDERSTANDING OF THE ESSENTIAL COMPONENTS OF THE MODULE. THE FIRST VIDEO SERVES AS AN INTRODUCTORY SESSION TO THE TOPIC OF THE MENTORING MODULE. THE SECOND VIDEO DELVES DEEPER INTO THE MODULE'S TOPICS, WHILE THE FINAL VIDEO FOCUSES ON THE MOST COMPLEX ASPECTS COVERED IN THE MENTORING MODULE.

CONTENT

VIDEO 1: THE VIDEO EXPLORES PROBLEM VALIDATION, STRESSING ITS IMPORTANCE IN BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT. IT HIGHLIGHTS THE NEED TO UNDERSTAND AND VALIDATE THE PROBLEM STATEMENT BEFORE STARTING ANY ENTREPRENEURIAL OR PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT PROJECT

VIDEO 2: THE VIDEO FOCUSES ON SOLUTION VALIDATION, EXPLAINING ITS SIGNIFICANCE, AND PROVIDING GUIDANCE ON HOW TO EXECUTE IT EFFECTIVELY. IT EMPHASIZES WHY VERIFYING THE VIABILITY OF A SOLUTION IS CRUCIAL BEFORE MOVING FORWARD WITH ANY BUSINESS OR PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT ENDEAVOR.

VIDEO 3: THE VIDEO IS ABOUT CRAFTING A COMPELLING VALUE PROPOSITION, WHICH IS ESSENTIALLY A CLEAR STATEMENT THAT EXPLAINS THE BENEFITS OF YOUR PRODUCT OR SERVICE AND WHY IT'S VALUABLE TO CUSTOMERS. IT DIVES INTO WHY HAVING A STRONG VALUE PROPOSITION IS ESSENTIAL FOR ATTRACTING AND RETAINING CUSTOMERS IN TODAY'S COMPETITIVE MARKET.

RESULTS

ALL TREE TRAINING VIDEOS HAVE BEEN PROVIDED BY THE MENTORING ORGANIZATION AND HAVE BEEN CONSUMED BY THE MENTEES.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 3H

QUIZ

STRUCTURE

ON THE F6S PLATFORM, A MULTIPLE-CHOICE QUIZ WAS IMPLEMENTED FOR EVERY MENTORING MODULE. THE AMOUNT OF QUESTIONS RANGED BETWEEN 24 AND 30. THE QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE THREE MENTORING VIDEOS. IT WAS ESTIMATED THAT THE COMPLETION OF ONE QUIZ TAKES ONE HOUR.

GOAL

THE QUIZ IS NON-MANDATORY BUT AIMS TO TEST THE MENTEES UNDERSTANDING OF MENTORING VIDEOS TO THEN FOCUS IN THE FOLLOWING MENTORING PROCESS ON AREAS WHERE THE PERFORMANCE IN THE QUIZ WAS LACKING.

CONTENT

THE QUIZ INCLUDES BOTH THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE CONTENT PRESENTED IN THE 3 VIDEOS OF THE MODULE. THE QUESTIONS ARE FORMED IN A WAY THAT MAKES IT EASY TO VERIFY WHETHER THE MENTEES HAVE INDEED WATCHED THE VIDEOS, AND TO IDENTIFY SPECIFIC AREAS ON WHICH THE TEAMS MAY NEED EXTRA CLARIFICATIONS.

RESULTS

UNFORTUNATELY, NONE OF THE TEAMS COMPLETED THE QUIZ.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

WORKSHOP

STRUCTURE

THE WORKSHOP SESSION IS THE FIRST LIVE INTERACTION OF THE MENTOR AND THE MENTEES. THE SESSION IS HELD ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THE WORKSHOP SESSION HAS A DURATION OF 2 HOURS AND IS OPEN FOR ALL MENTEES.

GOAL

IN THE WORKSHOP, THE DIFFERENT MENTEES CAN APPLY THE THEORETICAL CONCEPTS LEARNED IN THE TRAINING VIDEOS TO THEIR OWN BUSINESS ENDEAVOR.

CONTENT DURING THE WORKSHOP, A TOOL FOR PROBLEM VALIDATION WAS PRESENTED TO THE PARTICIPANTS. IT WAS DEMONSTRATED HOW THE TOOL FUNCTIONS, AND GUIDANCE WAS PROVIDED ON FILLING IN THE INITIAL HYPOTHESES TO BE TESTED IN THE MARKET. THE SESSION UTILIZED THE SUPPORT OF THE MENTI.COM ONLINE PLATFORM.

ALL FOUR TEAMS PARTICIPATED IN THE WORKSHOP AND UNDERSTOOD ITS CONTENT.

RESULTS THE WORKSHOP HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON 22/11/2023.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H

Q&A SESSION

STRUCTURE THE Q&A SESSION WAS FACILITATED ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THE DURATION OF THE SESSION WAS 1 HOUR AND OPEN FOR ALL MENTEES TO ENTER AND ASK QUESTIONS ABOUT MENTORING RELATED TOPICS.

GOAL THE Q&A SESSION AIMS TO PROVIDE THE MENTEES WITH AN OPPORTUNITY TO ASK QUESTIONS AND TO SOLVE DOUBTS RAISED FROM THE PREVIOUS TRAINING VIDEOS AND WORKSHOP.

CONTENT THE WORK ON PROBLEM VALIDATION CARRIED OUT BY THE TEAMS DURING THE WORKSHOP SESSION WAS REVIEWED, AND ALL THEIR DOUBTS AND QUESTIONS WERE ADDRESSED. FOLLOWING THAT, A TOOL FOR SOLUTION VALIDATION WAS PRESENTED.

ALL FOUR TEAMS ACTIVELY ENGAGED IN THE Q&A SESSION AND ASKED QUESTIONS.

RESULTS THE SESSION HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON 06/12/2023.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS

STRUCTURE TWO INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS FOR EACH START-UP, EACH WITH A DURATION OF ONE HOUR, WERE OFFERED ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR, LEADING TO A TOTAL OF TWO HOURS OF MENTORING PER START-UP. IN THESE SESSIONS ONLY, THE MENTORS AND ONE START-UP ARE PRESENT TO FOCUS ON THEIR SPECIFIC NEEDS AND ISSUES.

GOAL THE INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS PROVIDE PERSONALIZED GUIDANCE TO EACH START-UP, HELPING THEM OVERCOME SPECIFIC OBSTACLES ENCOUNTERED DURING CRITICAL PHASES OF THEIR COMPANIES. THIS ASSISTANCE AIDS IN DEVELOPING EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR THE FUTURE.

CONTENT IN THE INDIVIDUAL SESSION, THE PROBLEM VALIDATION PROCESS OF THE START-UPS WAS DISCUSSED.

RESULTS THE START-UP A COMMUNICATED THAT THEY HAD ISSUES TO ATTEND THE MENTORING SESSIONS. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY DID NOT GET A RESPONSE. HENCE, THE START-UP A DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

THE START-UP B PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS BMC (15/01/2024 & 22/01/2024) AND BASED ON THE DISCUSSION OF THE PROBLEM VALIDATION PROCESS IT WAS DECIDED THAT THE START-UP WILL START ANOTHER ROUND OF PROBLEM VALIDATION WITH ANOTHER GROUP OF POTENTIAL CUSTOMERS.

THE START-UP C PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (10/01/2024 & 22/01/2024) DURING WHICH THE PROBLEM VALIDATION, AND THE LACK OF ACCESS THE START-UP HAD TO THE INDUSTRY WERE DISCUSSED. FURTHER, ALTERNATIVE AVENUES TO CONTACT CUSTOMERS WERE SUGGESTED.

THE START-UP D COMMUNICATED THAT THEY HAD ISSUES TO ATTEND THE MENTORING SESSIONS. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY THE START-UP DECIDED TO NOT COMPLETE THIS MENTORING MODULE. HENCE, THE START-UP D DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H

REFLECTION SESSIONS

STRUCTURE

A ONE-HOUR REFLECTION SESSION WAS OFFERED TO ALL MENTEES ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THIS SESSION FOCUSED ON PROVIDING FEEDBACK TO THE MENTEES AND MARKED THE END OF THIS MENTORING MODULE

GOAL

THE REFLECTION SESSION AIMS TO ENCOURAGE PARTICIPANTS TO PRACTICE SELF-ASSESSMENT AND REFLECTION, ENABLING THEM TO MONITOR THEIR PROGRESS, ACKNOWLEDGE THEIR ACHIEVEMENTS, AND IDENTIFY AREAS FOR FUTURE DEVELOPMENT.

CONTENT

THE REFLECTION WAS HELD ON THE BASIS OF THE WORK PERFORMED ON THE PROBLEM VALIDATION TOOL. THE OVERALL INFORMATION GATHERED WAS ANALYSED AND STARTUPS WERE COACHED THROUGH THINKING ABOUT WHAT THE INFORMATION IMPLIED FOR THEIR BUSINESS.

THE START-UP C PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON 05/02/2024

THE START-UP B PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON 13/02/2024

BOTH STARTUPS ULTIMATELY REORIENTED THEIR BUSINESS OFFERING AS A RESULT OF THE INFORMATION THEY GATHERED: START-UP C CHANGED THEIR TARGET MARKET AND START-UP B CHANGED THE PROBLEM THEY WOULD LIKE TO ADDRESS.

RESULTS

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

4.3 FONDAZIONE E. AMALDI - YOUR IDEA PITCH: FROM TECH FEASIBILITY TO PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT

TRAINING VIDEOS

STRUCTURE

THE TRAINING VIDEOS SERVE AS THE INITIAL MENTORING ELEMENT, WITH EACH OF THE THREE VIDEOS LASTING ABOUT ONE HOUR, A TOTAL OF APPROXIMATELY THREE HOURS OF VIDEO MATERIAL IS PROVIDED. THE MENTORS PRE-RECORD THE VIDEOS, WHICH ARE THEN LINKED TO THE F6S PLATFORM

GOAL

THE TRAINING VIDEOS AIM TO INTRODUCE THE MENTEES INTO THE TOPIC OF THE MODULE AND PROVIDE THEM WITH A BASIC UNDERSTANDING OF THE ESSENTIAL COMPONENTS OF THE MODULE. THE FIRST VIDEO SERVES AS AN INTRODUCTORY SESSION TO THE TOPIC OF THE MENTORING MODULE. THE SECOND VIDEO DELVES DEEPER INTO THE MODULE'S TOPICS, WHILE THE FINAL VIDEO FOCUSES ON THE MOST COMPLEX ASPECTS COVERED IN THE MENTORING MODULE.

VIDEO 1: THE VIDEO FOCUSES ON THE "TECHNOLOGICAL FEASIBILITY" AND HAS THE AIM TO PROVIDE STUDENTS OR ASPIRING ENTREPRENEURS A PRELIMINARY BUT COMPREHENSIVE UNDERSTANDING ABOUT HOW TO DESIGN AND PERFORM A TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY STUDY. PRACTICAL TIPS, EXPLANATION OF METHODOLOGIES, EXAMPLES AND THEORETICAL REFERENCES ARE PROVIDED.

FIGURE 7: Screenshot of the first training video by Fondazione E. Amaldi

CONTENT

VIDEO 2: THE VIDEO FOCUSES ON "YOUR IDEA PITCH: FROM TECH FEASIBILITY TO PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT". THE OBJECTIVE OF THE VIDEO IS TO PROVIDE PARTICIPANTS A PRELIMINARY BUT COMPREHENSIVE EXPLANATION ABOUT HOW PRACTICALLY PUT THEM IN THE RIGHT ATTITUDE TO SOLVE COMPLEX PROBLEMS BY MEANS SOME OF THE MOST COMMON TOOLS OF THE DESIGN THINKING APPROACH: THE "PLANNING", THE "PROTOTYPING", THE "TESTING" AND THE "THINKING" ACTIVITY.

FIGURE 8: Screenshot of the second training video by Fondazione E. Amaldi

VIDEO 3: THE VIDEO FOCUSES ON “THE PITCH” AS AN EFFECTIVE MEANS TO PRESENT THE IDEA TO AN AUDIENCE. THE VIDEO EXPLAINS WHAT A PITCH IS, EXPLAINS THE DIFFERENT TYPOLOGIES OF PITCHES, PROVIDES SOME PRACTICAL TIPS TO PREPARE AND PERFORM WRITTEN AS WELL AS ORAL PITCHES.

FIGURE 9: Screenshot of the third training video by Fondazione E. Amaldi

ALL TREE TRAINING VIDEOS HAVE BEEN PROVIDED BY THE MENTORING ORGANIZATION AND HAVE BEEN CONSUMED BY THE MENTEES.

RESULTS

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 3H

QUIZ

STRUCTURE

ON THE F6S PLATFORM, A MULTIPLE-CHOICE QUIZ WAS IMPLEMENTED FOR EVERY MENTORING MODULE. THE AMOUNT OF QUESTIONS RANGED BETWEEN 24 AND 30. THE QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE THREE MENTORING VIDEOS. IT WAS ESTIMATED THAT THE COMPLETION OF ONE QUIZ TAKES ONE HOUR.

- GOAL** THE QUIZ IS NON-MANDATORY BUT AIMS TO TEST THE MENTEES UNDERSTANDING OF MENTORING VIDEOS TO THEN FOCUS IN THE FOLLOWING MENTORING PROCESS ON AREAS WHERE THE PERFORMANCE IN THE QUIZ WAS LACKING.
- CONTENT** THE QUIZ INCLUDES BOTH THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE CONTENT PRESENTED IN THE 3 VIDEOS OF THE MODULE. THE QUESTIONS ARE FORMED IN A WAY THAT MAKES IT EASY TO VERIFY WHETHER THE MENTEES HAVE INDEED WATCHED THE VIDEOS, AND TO IDENTIFY SPECIFIC AREAS ON WHICH THE TEAMS MAY NEED EXTRA CLARIFICATIONS.
- RESULTS** UNFORTUNATELY, NONE OF THE TEAMS COMPLETED THE QUIZ.
TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

WORKSHOP

- STRUCTURE** THE WORKSHOP SESSION IS THE FIRST LIVE INTERACTION OF THE MENTOR AND THE MENTEES. THE SESSION IS HELD ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THE WORKSHOP SESSION HAS A DURATION OF 2 HOURS AND IS OPEN FOR ALL MENTEES.
- GOAL** IN THE WORKSHOP, THE DIFFERENT MENTEES CAN APPLY THE THEORETICAL CONCEPTS LEARNED IN THE TRAINING VIDEOS TO THEIR OWN BUSINESS ENDEAVORS.
- CONTENT** THE WORKSHOP ON "IDEA PITCH AND PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT" WITH GUIDED EXERCISES AIMED TO TRANSLATE THEORETICAL CONCEPTS FROM VIDEO LECTURES INTO PRACTICAL SKILLS FOR EFFECTIVELY COMMUNICATING A BUSINESS IDEA AND DRAFTING A PRODUCT OR SERVICE DEVELOPMENT PLAN. IT PROVIDED PRACTICAL HINTS AND TIPS ON VARIOUS TYPES OF PITCHES FOR DIFFERENT SITUATIONS, ALONG WITH EXAMPLES ON INITIATING A PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT PLAN. THE WORKSHOP REFERRED TO THE 'DESIGN THINKING APPROACH' AND ADVISED ON TYPICAL TOPICS TO CONSIDER FOR DRAFTING AN EFFECTIVE AND COHESIVE TECHNOLOGY-BASED PRODUCT OR SERVICE DEVELOPMENT PLAN. ADDITIONALLY, TEMPLATES AND TOOLS WERE PROVIDED TO FACILITATE THE PROCESS.
- ALL FOUR TEAMS PARTICIPATED IN THE WORKSHOP AND UNDERSTOOD ITS CONTENT.
- RESULTS** THE WORKSHOP HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON 21/11/2023.
TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H

Q&A SESSION

- STRUCTURE** THE Q&A SESSION WAS FACILITATED ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THE DURATION OF THE SESSION WAS 1 HOUR AND OPEN FOR ALL MENTEES TO ENTER AND ASK QUESTIONS ABOUT MENTORING RELATED TOPICS.
- GOAL** THE Q&A SESSION AIMS TO PROVIDE THE MENTEES WITH AN OPPORTUNITY TO ASK QUESTIONS AND TO SOLVE DOUBTS RAISED FROM THE PREVIOUS TRAINING VIDEOS AND WORKSHOP.

- CONTENT** DURING THE SESSION, A QUICK SUMMARY OF THE MAIN TOPICS EXPLAINED IN THE PREVIOUS TRAINING VIDEOS AND WORKSHOP WAS PROVIDED. THIS WAS FOLLOWED UP BY ANSWERING QUESTIONS OF THE MENTEES RELATED TO GENERAL TOPICS, PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT AND PARTICULAR COMPANY IDEAS AND PLANS.
- ALL FOUR TEAMS ACTIVELY ENGAGED IN THE Q&A SESSION AND ASKED QUESTIONS.
- RESULTS** THE SESSION HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON 12/12/2023.
- TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H**

INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS

- STRUCTURE** TWO INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS FOR EACH START-UP, EACH WITH A DURATION OF ONE HOUR, WERE OFFERED ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR, LEADING TO A TOTAL OF TWO HOURS OF MENTORING PER START-UP. IN THESE SESSIONS ONLY, THE MENTORS AND ONE START-UP ARE PRESENT TO FOCUS ON THEIR SPECIFIC NEEDS AND ISSUES.
- GOAL** THE INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS PROVIDE PERSONALIZED GUIDANCE TO EACH START-UP, HELPING THEM OVERCOME SPECIFIC OBSTACLES ENCOUNTERED DURING CRITICAL PHASES OF THEIR COMPANIES. THIS ASSISTANCE AIDS IN DEVELOPING EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR THE FUTURE.
- CONTENT** THE INDIVIDUAL SESSION CAN COVER A RANGE OF TOPICS, DEEPENING ON THE MENTEES NEEDS. THEY CAN FOCUS ON PRACTICAL ADVICES TO IMPROVE THE CLARITY IN PRESENTING YOUR IDEA, THE EXPLANATION OF METHODOLOGIES TO IMPROVE THE PLANNING AND TESTING PROCESS OF THE COMPANY PRODUCT OR SUPPORTING TO PREPARE THE TEAM IN FUTURE MEETINGS WITH POTENTIAL INVESTORS.
- RESULTS** THE START-UP A COMMUNICATED THAT THEY HAD ISSUES TO ATTEND THE MENTORING SESSIONS. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY DID NOT GET A RESPONSE. HENCE, THE START-UP A DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.
- THE START-UP B PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (17/01/2024 AND 24/01/2024) DURING WHICH THE STARTUP REVIEWED ITS PRESENTATION WITH THE MENTOR, TRYING TO PROPOSE ALTERNATIVE WAYS TO CONSIDER THE IDENTIFIED STAKEHOLDERS (CUSTOMERS, USERS, COMPETITORS, ETC.). THE INDIVIDUAL SESSION HAS BEEN FOCUSED ON THE IN-DEPTH EXPLANATION OF SPECIFIC TOPICS OF THE "PITCH", IN PARTICULAR, WHICH KIND OF PITCH IS MORE SUITABLE IN CASE OF A PRESENTATION TO POTENTIAL INVESTORS AND TO POTENTIAL CUSTOMERS. THE MENTOR HAS SUGGESTED TIPS ABOUT HOW TO PREPARE AND PERFORM AN INVESTOR DECK, ESPECIALLY IN WRITTEN FORM, USING AN APPROPRIATE STRUCTURE. DIFFERENCES BETWEEN CUSTOMERS AND STAKEHOLDERS HAS BEEN EXPLAINED; A REVIEW ABOUT THE FINANCIAL FORECAST HAS BEEN REQUESTED AND SUGGESTIONS PROVIDED TO BETTER PRESENT FINANCIAL FORECASTS.
- THE START-UP C PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (16/01/2024 AND 23/01/2024) DURING WHICH THE STARTUP REVIEWED ITS PRESENTATION WITH THE MENTOR, TRYING TO BETTER EXPLAIN THEIR BUSINESS PROPOSITION AND PRICING MODEL. THE TEAM ALSO TRIED TO BETTER IDENTIFY THE POTENTIAL CUSTOMERS AND INVESTORS. THE INDIVIDUAL SESSION HAS BEEN FOCUSED ON THE IN-DEPTH EXPLANATION OF SPECIFIC TOPICS OF THE "PITCH", IN PARTICULAR, HIGHLIGHTING DIFFERENCES BETWEEN SALES PITCH AND INVESTOR DECK, EXPLAINING STRATEGIES TO PERFORM AD HOC PRESENTATIONS OF THE IDEA BASED ON DIFFERENT KINDS OF AUDIENCES. A REVIEW OF THE PRESENTATION OF THE STARTUP HAS BEEN PERFORMED BY THE MENTOR, PROVIDING TIPS TO TRANSFORM IT INTO

AN INVESTOR DECK, WORKING ESPECIALLY ON THE FINAL PART, NOT PROVIDED BY FINAL CONCLUSIONS AND REQUESTS.

THE START-UP D COMMUNICATED THAT THEY HAD ISSUES TO ATTEND THE MENTORING SESSIONS. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION BUT UNFORTUNATELY THE START-UP DECIDED TO NOT COMPLETE THIS MENTORING MODULE. HENCE, THE START-UP D DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H

REFLECTION SESSIONS

STRUCTURE

A ONE-HOUR REFLECTION SESSION WAS OFFERED TO ALL MENTEES ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THIS SESSION FOCUSED ON PROVIDING FEEDBACK TO THE MENTEES AND MARKED THE END OF THIS MENTORING MODULE

GOAL

THE REFLECTION SESSION AIMS TO ENCOURAGE PARTICIPANTS TO PRACTICE SELF-ASSESSMENT AND REFLECTION, ENABLING THEM TO MONITOR THEIR PROGRESS, ACKNOWLEDGE THEIR ACHIEVEMENTS, AND IDENTIFY AREAS FOR FUTURE DEVELOPMENT.

CONTENT

A REVIEW OF THE OVERALL MENTORING PATH HAS BEEN MADE, FOCUSING ON THE MAIN CRITICAL POINT ON THE BASE OF THE STARTUP SENSIBILITY. FUTURE PLANS HAVE ALSO BEEN ANALYZED.

RESULTS

THE START-UP B PARTICIPATED IN THE REFLECTION SESSION (21/02/2024). A REVIEW OF THE OVERALL MENTORING PATH HAS BEEN MADE, FOCUSING ON THE MAIN CRITICAL POINT ON THE BASE OF THE STARTUP SENSIBILITY: IN PARTICULAR, THE FINANCIAL FORECAST OF THE COMPANY AND METHODOLOGIES TO CALCULATE THE VALUE OF ENTERPRISES, IDENTIFIED AS MAIN WEAKNESS POINTS BY THE STARTUP. FUTURE PLANS HAVE ALSO BEEN PLANNED, WITH A DISCUSSION OF THE POTENTIAL FUNDING OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE BACKWARDS STRATEGIES AND SERVICES, AT EUROPEAN AS WELL AS NATIONAL LEVEL. THE STARTUP HAS PROACTIVELY INTERACTED OPENLY SHARING CRITICAL POINTS AND NEEDS TO OVERCOME SOME MANAGERIAL ISSUES (E.G. CAPACITY TO PERFORM AND PRESENT FINANCIAL FORECASTS AND TO IDENTIFY FINANCIAL RESOURCES TO COVER INVESTMENTS AND COSTS).

THE START-UP C PARTICIPATED IN THE REFLECTION SESSION (19/02/2024). A REVIEW OF THE OVERALL MENTORING PATH HAS BEEN MADE, FOCUSING ON THE FINANCIAL FORECAST OF THE COMPANY AND METHODOLOGIES TO ENGAGE CUSTOMERS AND STAKEHOLDERS. THE SESSION HAS ALSO BEEN FOCUSED ON THE ASSESSMENT OF THE ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE OF THE TEAM, WHICH SEEMED LACKING ALL THE NECESSARY EXPERTISE TO LAUNCH THE SERVICE ON THE MARKET. THE STARTUP HAS INTERACTED WITH THE MENTOR, REFLECTING ABOUT THE MAIN CRITICAL ISSUE OF THE COMPANY: THE LACK OF A TEAM WITH ALL THE NEEDED SKILLS AND EXPERTISE (MARKETING) TO IMPLEMENT THE PROJECT IDEA. THE STARTUP HAS AGREED ON THE NEED TO WORK ON THIS POINT BEFORE PERFORMING FURTHER COMMERCIAL ACTIVITIES.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

4.4 EBAN - INVESTMENT PITCH AND QUANTIFYING YOUR FUNDING NEEDS

TRAINING VIDEOS

STRUCTURE

THE TRAINING VIDEOS SERVE AS THE INITIAL MENTORING ELEMENT, WITH EACH OF THE THREE VIDEOS LASTING ABOUT ONE HOUR, A TOTAL OF APPROXIMATELY THREE HOURS OF VIDEO MATERIAL IS PROVIDED. THE MENTORS PRE-RECORD THE VIDEOS, WHICH ARE THEN LINKED TO ON THE F6S PLATFORM.

GOAL

THE TRAINING VIDEOS AIM TO INTRODUCE THE MENTEES INTO THE TOPIC OF THE MODULE AND PROVIDE THEM WITH A STRONG BASE FOR UNDERSTANDING OF THE ESSENTIAL COMPONENTS OF THE MODULE: INVESTMENT PITCH AND QUANTIFYING YOUR FUNDING NEEDS. THE FIRST VIDEO PRESENTED THE CORE PRINCIPLES AND SKILLS TO DELIVER A COMPELLING INVESTMENT PITCH, PROVIDING THE APPROPRIATE STRUCTURE AND COMPONENTS TO CRAFT THE PITCH ACCORDING TO THE DIFFERENT FUNDING SOURCES. THE SECOND VIDEO PRESENTED AND DESCRIBED THE DIFFERENT FUNDING SOURCES AVAILABLE FOR STARTUPS, WHILE THE FINAL VIDEO FOCUSES ON THE FINANCIAL FORECASTING AND THE QUANTIFYING OF THEIR NEEDS.

CONTENT

VIDEO 1: THE VIDEO DIVED INTO THE ART OF INVESTMENT PITCHING. BY THE END OF THE WEBINARS, PARTICIPANTS SHOULD HAVE ACQUIRED A SOLID UNDERSTANDING OF WHAT IS AN INVESTMENT PITCH, HOW THEY ARE OFTEN STRUCTURED AND WHAT EACH PHASE CONSISTS OF. THE VIDEO LESSON ALSO TACKLES THE IMPORTANCE OF THE SOFT SKILL OF STORYTELLING AND THE NEED TO TAILOR THE INVESTMENT PITCH ACCORDING TO THE DIFFERENT AUDIENCES.

VIDEO 2: IN THIS VIDEO, THE MENTOR COVERED IN DETAIL THE DIFFERENT FUNDING SOURCES. BY THE END OF THE WEBINARS, PARTICIPANTS SHOULD BE ABLE TO UNDERSTAND THE DIFFERENT STAGES A STARTUP WILL BE IN AND WHAT WOULD BE THEIR RESPECTIVE IDEAL SOURCE OF FUNDING TO GUARANTEE THEIR FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY. THE WEBINAR ALSO COVERED WHAT WOULD BE THE MOST ADEQUATE EQUITY PERCENTAGES TO GIVE AWAY DURING EACH PHASE.

VIDEO 3: IN THIS VIDEO, THE MENTOR COVERED FINANCIAL FORECASTING AND QUANTIFYING NEEDS. IT IS ESSENTIAL TO UNDERSTAND THESE TOPICS SINCE THEY WOULD ULTIMATELY HELP THE PARTICIPANTS UNDERSTAND THE FINANCIAL REQUIREMENTS OF THEIR BUSINESS, INCLUDING HOW MUCH CAPITAL THEY WOULD EVENTUALLY NEED TO RAISE AND HOW IT WILL BE USED. THE WEBINAR THEREFORE DIVED INTO THE FINANCIAL PROJECTIONS, MARKET SIZE AND MARKET SHARE TARGETS, KEY FINANCIAL METRICS AND KPIS, EXIT STRATEGIES AND OTHER ESSENTIAL POINTS.

ALL THREE TRAINING VIDEOS HAVE BEEN PROVIDED BY THE MENTORING ORGANIZATION AND HAVE BEEN CONSUMED BY THE MENTEES.

RESULTS

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 3H

Quiz

STRUCTURE

ON THE F6S PLATFORM, A MULTIPLE-CHOICE QUIZ WAS IMPLEMENTED FOR EVERY MENTORING MODULE. THE AMOUNT OF QUESTIONS RANGED BETWEEN 24 AND 30. THE QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE THREE MENTORING VIDEOS. IT WAS ESTIMATED THAT THE COMPLETION OF ONE QUIZ TAKES ONE HOUR.

GOAL

THE QUIZ IS NON-MANDATORY BUT AIMS TO TEST THE MENTEES UNDERSTANDING OF MENTORING VIDEOS TO THEN FOCUS IN THE FOLLOWING MENTORING PROCESS ON AREAS WHERE THE PERFORMANCE IN THE QUIZ WAS LACKING.

CONTENT

THE QUIZ SHARED BY EBAN INCLUDES QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE CONTENT PRESENTED IN THE 3 VIDEOS OF THE MODULE. EACH VIDEO HAS 8 DEDICATED QUESTIONS WITH 4 POSSIBLE ANSWERS EACH. THE GOAL IS TO ASSESS THE LEVEL OF UNDERSTANDING WITH QUESTIONS THAT WERE BASED ON WHAT WAS PRESENTED ON THE SLIDES - OFFERING THE OPPORTUNITY FOR THE PARTICIPANTS TO GET BACK TO THE PRESENTATION TO MAKE SURE THEY DID NOT MISS ANY OF THE IMPORTANT INFORMATION WORTH REMEMBERING.

RESULTS

UNFORTUNATELY, NONE OF THE TEAMS COMPLETED THE QUIZ.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

WORKSHOP

STRUCTURE

THE WORKSHOP SESSION IS THE FIRST LIVE INTERACTION OF THE MENTOR AND THE MENTEES. THE SESSION IS HELD ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THE WORKSHOP SESSION HAS A DURATION OF 2 HOURS AND IS OPEN FOR ALL MENTEES.

GOAL

IN THE WORKSHOP, THE DIFFERENT MENTEES CAN APPLY THE THEORETICAL CONCEPTS LEARNED IN THE TRAINING VIDEOS TO THEIR OWN BUSINESS ENDEAVORS.

CONTENT

IN THE WORKSHOP, THE MENTOR BEGAN THE SESSION WITH A FIRST ROUND OF INTRODUCTION TO INITIALLY ASSESS THE WAY THE ENTREPRENEURS PRESENTED THEMSELVES (ELEVATOR PITCH) MAKING SURE THAT THE STARTUPS WERE ABLE TO PROVIDE A CONCISE AND YET INTERESTING PRESENTATION OF THEMSELVES, TO POTENTIALLY ATTRACT THE INTEREST OF AN INVESTOR DURING A NETWORKING EVENT.

THE MENTOR ALSO COVERED ALL THE KEY POINTS PRESENTED DURING THE VIDEOS LESSON, MAKING SURE THAT THE PARTICIPANTS WERE UP TO DATE AND WERE ABLE TO PROCEED WITH THE PREPARATION OF A FIRST DRAFT OF THEIR PITCH. FOCUSING ON HOW TO EFFECTIVELY DELIVER A PITCH, ENGAGING PARTICIPANTS, REQUESTING THEM TO ATTEMPT COVERING EACH POINT AND ENCOURAGING QUESTION EXCHANGES.

RESULTS

ONLY TWO TEAMS PARTICIPATED IN THE WORKSHOP (C AND B) AND ALL OF THEM UNDERSTOOD ITS CONTENT. THE SESSION WAS RECORDED TO ENABLE ENTREPRENEURS WHO MISSED THE SESSION TO WATCH IT.

THE WORKSHOP WAS CONDUCTED ON 28/11/2024.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H

Q&A SESSION

STRUCTURE	THE Q&A SESSION WAS FACILITATED ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THE DURATION OF THE SESSION WAS 1 HOUR AND OPEN FOR ALL MENTEES TO ENTER AND ASK QUESTIONS ABOUT MENTORING RELATED TOPICS.
GOAL	THE Q&A SESSION AIMS TO PROVIDE THE MENTEES WITH AN OPPORTUNITY TO ASK QUESTIONS AND TO SOLVE DOUBTS RAISED FROM THE PREVIOUS TRAINING VIDEOS AND WORKSHOP. THE MENTOR ADDRESSED ALL PRESSING QUESTIONS THAT AROSE DURING THE WEBINARS AND THE WORKSHOP, AND GUIDED PARTICIPANTS INTO HOW TO REFINE THEIR OBJECTIVES AND PITCH TO PRESENT TO INVESTORS.
CONTENT	THE MENTOR SET THE FOUNDATION FOR FUTURE DISCUSSION IN THE ONE-TO-ONE SESSIONS, ENSURING THE PARTICIPANTS UNDERSTOOD ALL THE POINTS, EVEN IF THEY MIGHT NOT HAVE ASKED A QUESTION ON THIS SPECIFIC POINT. ONLY THREE TEAMS PARTICIPATED IN THE WORKSHOP (A, C, AND B) AND ALL OF THEM PARTICIPATED AND ASKED QUESTIONS. THE SESSION WAS RECORDED TO ENABLE ENTREPRENEURS WHO MISSED THE SESSION TO WATCH IT.
RESULTS	THE Q&A SESSION WAS CONDUCTED ON 16/01/2024. TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS

STRUCTURE	TWO INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS FOR EACH START-UP, EACH WITH A DURATION OF ONE HOUR, WERE OFFERED ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR, LEADING TO A TOTAL OF TWO HOURS OF MENTORING PER START-UP. IN THESE SESSIONS ONLY, THE MENTORS AND ONE START-UP ARE PRESENT TO FOCUS ON THEIR SPECIFIC NEEDS AND ISSUES.
GOAL	THE INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS PROVIDE PERSONALIZED GUIDANCE TO EACH START-UP, HELPING THEM OVERCOME SPECIFIC OBSTACLES ENCOUNTERED DURING CRITICAL PHASES OF THEIR COMPANIES. THIS ASSISTANCE AIDS IN DEVELOPING EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR THE FUTURE.
CONTENT	THE INDIVIDUAL SESSION FOCUSED ON RESOLVING REMAINING QUESTIONS AND PROVIDING ADDITIONAL MATERIAL RELATED TO FUNDING SOURCES AND PITCHING. THE START-UP A COMMUNICATED THAT THEY HAD ISSUES TO ATTEND THE MENTORING SESSIONS. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY DID NOT GET A RESPONSE. HENCE, THE START-UP A DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.
RESULTS	THE START-UP B PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (13/02/2024 & 19/02/2024) AND DURING THIS SESSION, THE MENTOR ANSWERED ADDITIONAL QUESTIONS THE ENTREPRENEUR HAD, AND THEN THEY ALSO FOCUSED ON PROVIDING ADDITIONAL SUPPORT AND MATERIALS TO BETTER UNDERSTAND THE DIFFERENT

FUNDING SOURCES, THE SHARE DILUTION AND HOW TO CRAFT A PITCH ACCORDINGLY. EBAN MENTOR ALSO SHARED AN ADDITIONAL EXERCISE DURING THE FIRST ONE-TO-ONE MEETING FOR THE STARTUP THAT THE MENTOR REVIEWED IN THE FOLLOWING MEETING, MAKING SURE THE PARTICIPANT UNDERSTOOD THE ASSIGNMENT AND PROVIDED FINAL FEEDBACK FOR THEIR PITCH. INDEED, A PITCH DRY RUN WAS ORGANIZED IN WHICH THE MENTOR ASKED POTENTIAL INVESTORS QUESTIONS.

THE START-UP C PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (01/02/2024 & 14/02/2024) DURING WHICH THE MENTOR ANSWERED ADDITIONAL QUESTIONS THE ENTREPRENEUR HAD, AND THEN THEY ALSO FOCUSED ON PROVIDING ADDITIONAL SUPPORT AND MATERIALS TO BETTER UNDERSTAND THE DIFFERENT FUNDING SOURCES, THE SHARE DILUTION AND HOW TO CRAFT A PITCH ACCORDINGLY. EBAN MENTOR ALSO SHARED AN ADDITIONAL EXERCISE DURING THE FIRST ONE-TO-ONE MEETING FOR THE STARTUP THAT THE MENTOR REVIEWED IN THE FOLLOWING MEETING MAKING SURE THE PARTICIPANT UNDERSTOOD THE ASSIGNMENT AND PROVIDED FINAL FEEDBACK FOR THEIR PITCH. INDEED, A PITCH DRY RUN WAS ORGANIZED IN WHICH THE MENTOR ASKED POTENTIAL INVESTORS QUESTIONS.

THE START-UP D COMMUNICATED THAT THEY HAD ISSUES TO ATTEND THE MENTORING SESSIONS. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY THE START-UP DECIDED TO NOT COMPLETE THIS MENTORING MODULE. HENCE, THE START-UP D DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H

REFLECTION SESSIONS

STRUCTURE

A ONE-HOUR REFLECTION SESSION WAS OFFERED TO ALL MENTEES ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THIS SESSION FOCUSED ON PROVIDING FEEDBACK TO THE MENTEES AND MARKED THE END OF THIS MENTORING MODULE

GOAL

THE REFLECTION SESSION AIMS TO ENCOURAGE PARTICIPANTS TO PRACTICE SELF-ASSESSMENT AND REFLECTION, ENABLING THEM TO MONITOR THEIR PROGRESS, ACKNOWLEDGE THEIR ACHIEVEMENTS, AND IDENTIFY AREAS FOR FUTURE DEVELOPMENT.

CONTENT

EBAN HAS HAD ITS SESSION WITH C BUT DID NOT HAVE THE SESSION YET WITH B (THE SESSION WAS PLANNED TO TAKE PLACE ON THE 8TH OF MARCH BUT THE ENTREPRENEUR REQUESTED TO RESCHEDULE THE SESSION ON THE 19/03/2024).

EBAN OFFERED THE OPPORTUNITY TO START-UP C TO ASK THEIR FINAL QUESTIONS CONCERNING THE COURSE AND TO HAVE A FINAL PITCH DRY RUN TO CONSOLIDATE THE LESSONS LEARNED DURING THE FIRST HALF OF THE SESSION. EBAN HAS ALSO PRESENTED THE INITIATIVES AND THEIR ANNUAL EVENTS EBAN IS CURRENTLY ORGANIZED AND INVOLVED IN, WHICH COULD PROVIDE ADDITIONAL SUPPORT TO THE TEAMS, (SUCH AS HORIZON PROJECTS, AND ITS CONGRESS). THE PARTICIPANT REQUESTED WHETHER THEY COULD REACH OUT TO EBAN IN CASE THEY HAD ANY ADDITIONAL QUESTIONS, OR MATERIAL TO BE REVIEWED, AND EBAN GLADLY ACCEPTED AND ENCOURAGED THE ENTREPRENEUR TO NOT HESITATE TO REACH OUT EVEN ONCE THE PROJECT WAS OVER. THEN EBAN ENCOURAGED THE PARTICIPANTS TO SHARE THEIR THOUGHTS ABOUT THE SESSION AND PRACTICE SELF-ASSESSMENT TO ACKNOWLEDGE THEIR ACHIEVEMENTS. THE PARTICIPANTS HAVE ALSO AGREED TO COMPLETE A SURVEY THAT EBAN SHARED OFFERING THE PARTICIPANTS TO PROVIDE VALUABLE FEEDBACK ON THE COURSE.

RESULTS

THE START-UP B WILL HAVE THEIR SESSION ON THE 19/03/2024

THE START-UP C PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 11/03/2024

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

4.5 CORALLIA - ENTREPRENEURIAL BUSINESS PLANNING

TRAINING VIDEOS

STRUCTURE	THE TRAINING VIDEOS SERVE AS THE INITIAL MENTORING ELEMENT, WITH EACH OF THE THREE VIDEOS LASTING ABOUT ONE HOUR, A TOTAL OF APPROXIMATELY THREE HOURS OF VIDEO MATERIAL IS PROVIDED. THE MENTORS PRE-RECORD THE VIDEOS, WHICH ARE THEN LINKED TO ON THE F6S PLATFORM.
GOAL	THE TRAINING VIDEOS AIM TO INTRODUCE THE MENTEES INTO THE TOPIC OF THE MODULE AND PROVIDE THEM WITH A BASIC UNDERSTANDING OF THE ESSENTIAL COMPONENTS OF THE MODULE. THE FIRST VIDEO SERVES AS AN INTRODUCTORY SESSION TO THE TOPIC OF THE MENTORING MODULE. THE SECOND VIDEO DELVES DEEPER INTO THE MODULE'S TOPICS, WHILE THE FINAL VIDEO FOCUSES ON THE MOST COMPLEX ASPECTS COVERED IN THE MENTORING MODULE.
CONTENT	VIDEO 1: THE VIDEO INTRODUCES PARTICIPANTS TO THE FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLES OF BUSINESS PLANNING. IT AIMS FOR VIEWERS TO GRASP THE SIGNIFICANCE OF A BUSINESS PLAN, COMPREHEND ITS ESSENTIAL COMPONENTS, AND GAIN INSIGHTS INTO INITIATING THE DRAFTING PROCESS FOR THEIR STARTUP. DETAILED INFORMATION AND SUGGESTIONS REGARDING THE MANDATORY SECTIONS OF A BUSINESS PLAN, SUCH AS THE EXECUTIVE SUMMARY, COMPANY DESCRIPTION, MARKET ANALYSIS, ORGANIZATION AND MANAGEMENT, SERVICE OR PRODUCT LINE, MARKETING AND SALES, AND FINANCIAL PROJECTIONS, ARE PROVIDED. THE ADVICE GIVEN IS GROUNDED IN BEST PRACTICES FOR WRITING A BUSINESS PLAN.

Figure 10: Screenshot of the first training video by Corallia

VIDEO 2: THE VIDEO AIMS TO GUIDE PARTICIPANTS ON CONDUCTING A COMPREHENSIVE MARKET ANALYSIS AND DEVELOPING EFFECTIVE BUSINESS STRATEGIES. IT IS INTENDED THAT, BY THE END OF THE WEBINARS, PARTICIPANTS WILL BE ABLE TO CONDUCT A MARKET ANALYSIS, ENCOMPASSING A COMPETITIVE ANALYSIS AND CUSTOMER SEGMENTATION, AND TO FORMULATE A SUITABLE BUSINESS STRATEGY. THE WEBINAR CENTERS ON EMPHASIZING THE IMPORTANCE OF UNDERSTANDING THE MARKET LANDSCAPE, WHICH INCLUDES IDENTIFYING COMPETITORS, COMPREHENDING CUSTOMER SEGMENTS, AND RECOGNIZING MARKET TRENDS.

Figure 11: Screenshot of the second training video by Corallia

VIDEO 3: THE VIDEO AIMS TO EQUIP PARTICIPANTS WITH THE KNOWLEDGE AND SKILLS REQUIRED TO EFFECTIVELY PLAN THE FINANCIAL ASPECTS OF THEIR BUSINESS. IT IS INTENDED THAT, BY THE END OF THE WEBINAR, PARTICIPANTS WILL BE CAPABLE OF CREATING BUDGETS, FINANCIAL FORECASTS, AND A PLAN FOR FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT FOR THEIR START-UPS. THE VIDEO COVERS THE FUNDAMENTALS OF FINANCIAL PLANNING, INCLUDING BUDGETING, CASH FLOW MANAGEMENT, FINANCIAL FORECASTING, AND UNDERSTANDING KEY FINANCIAL STATEMENTS.

Figure 12: Screenshot of the third training video by Corallia

RESULTS

ALL THREE TRAINING VIDEOS HAVE BEEN PROVIDED BY THE MENTORING ORGANIZATION AND HAVE BEEN CONSUMED BY THE MENTEES.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 3H

QUIZ

STRUCTURE

ON THE F6S PLATFORM, A MULTIPLE-CHOICE QUIZ WAS IMPLEMENTED FOR EVERY MENTORING MODULE. THE AMOUNT OF QUESTIONS RANGED BETWEEN 24 AND 30. THE QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE THREE MENTORING VIDEOS. IT WAS ESTIMATED THAT THE COMPLETION OF ONE QUIZ TAKES ONE HOUR.

GOAL

THE QUIZ IS NON-MANDATORY BUT AIMS TO TEST THE MENTEES UNDERSTANDING OF MENTORING VIDEOS TO THEN FOCUS IN THE FOLLOWING MENTORING PROCESS ON AREAS WHERE THE PERFORMANCE IN THE QUIZ WAS LACKING.

CONTENT

THE QUIZ INCLUDES BOTH THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE CONTENT PRESENTED IN THE 3 VIDEOS OF THE MODULE. THE QUESTIONS ARE FORMED IN A WAY THAT MAKES IT EASY TO VERIFY WHETHER THE MENTEES HAVE INDEED WATCHED THE VIDEOS, AND TO IDENTIFY SPECIFIC AREAS ON WHICH THE TEAMS MAY NEED EXTRA CLARIFICATIONS.

RESULTS

UNFORTUNATELY, NONE OF THE TEAMS COMPLETED THE QUIZ.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

WORKSHOP

- STRUCTURE** THE WORKSHOP SESSION IS THE FIRST LIVE INTERACTION OF THE MENTOR AND THE MENTEES. THE SESSION IS HELD ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THE WORKSHOP SESSION HAS A DURATION OF 2 HOURS AND IS OPEN FOR ALL MENTEES.
- GOAL** IN THE WORKSHOP, THE DIFFERENT MENTEES CAN APPLY THE THEORETICAL CONCEPTS LEARNED IN THE TRAINING VIDEOS TO THEIR OWN BUSINESS ENDEAVOR.
- CONTENT** THE PRIMARY AIM OF THIS WORKSHOP WAS TO ENABLE PARTICIPANTS TO APPLY THE CONCEPTS LEARNT DURING THE WEBINARS TO DRAFT THEIR BUSINESS PLANS. BY THE END OF THE WORKSHOP, EACH TEAM IDENTIFIED A PRELIMINARY OUTLINE OF THEIR BUSINESS PLAN AND UNDERSTOOD THE AREAS THEY NEED TO DEVELOP FURTHER. AT THE BEGINNING OF THE WORKSHOP, THE PARTICIPANTS PRESENTED THEIR IDEAS AND WITH THE HELP OF THE MENTOR, THEY IDENTIFIED THE TYPE OF THEIR BUSINESS MODEL AND THEIR MARKET SEGMENT. THE BUSINESS PLAN ANALYSIS THAT FOLLOWED FOR EACH COMPONENT OF THE BUSINESS PLAN WAS BASED ON EXAMPLES THAT FIT EXACTLY THE IDEAS AND MARKETS OF THE PARTICIPANTS, AND AS SUCH, THE PRESENTATION OF THE BUSINESS PLAN STRUCTURE WAS TAILORED TO THE INDIVIDUAL NEEDS OF THE TEAMS.
- ALL FOUR TEAMS PARTICIPATED IN THE WORKSHOP AND UNDERSTOOD ITS CONTENT.
- RESULTS** THE WORKSHOP HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON 29/11/2023.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H

Q&A SESSION

- STRUCTURE** THE Q&A SESSION WAS FACILITATED ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THE DURATION OF THE SESSION WAS 1 HOUR AND OPEN FOR ALL MENTEES TO ENTER AND ASK QUESTIONS ABOUT MENTORING RELATED TOPICS.
- GOAL** THE Q&A SESSION AIMS TO PROVIDE THE MENTEES WITH AN OPPORTUNITY TO ASK QUESTIONS AND TO SOLVE DOUBTS RAISED FROM THE PREVIOUS TRAINING VIDEOS AND WORKSHOP.
- CONTENT** DURING THIS SESSION, THE MENTOR ADDRESSED ALL QUESTIONS AND ISSUES THAT AROSE DURING THE WEBINARS AND THE WORKSHOP, AND PROVIDED PARTICIPANTS WITH THE CLARIFICATION AND GUIDANCE NEEDED TO REFINE THEIR OWN BUSINESS PLANS. MOREOVER, THE TIME-PLAN AND METHODOLOGY TO BE FOLLOWED DURING THE UPCOMING INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS WAS ALSO PRESENTED.
- ALL FOUR TEAMS ACTIVELY ENGAGED IN THE Q&A SESSION AND ASKED QUESTIONS.
- RESULTS** THE SESSION WAS CONDUCTED ON 15/12/2023.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS

STRUCTURE

TWO INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS FOR EACH START-UP, EACH WITH A DURATION OF ONE HOUR, WERE OFFERED ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR, LEADING TO A TOTAL OF TWO HOURS OF MENTORING PER START-UP. IN THESE SESSIONS ONLY, THE MENTORS AND ONE START-UP ARE PRESENT TO FOCUS ON THEIR SPECIFIC NEEDS AND ISSUES.

GOAL

THE INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS PROVIDE PERSONALIZED GUIDANCE TO EACH START-UP, HELPING THEM OVERCOME SPECIFIC OBSTACLES ENCOUNTERED DURING CRITICAL PHASES OF THEIR COMPANIES. THIS ASSISTANCE AIDS IN DEVELOPING EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR THE FUTURE.

CONTENT

IN THE INDIVIDUAL SESSION, THE TEAMS HAD THE CHANCE TO CONTINUE WORKING ON THEIR BUSINESS PLAN AND CLARIFY PRESSING ISSUES.

THE START-UP A COMMUNICATED THAT THEY HAD ISSUES TO ATTEND THE MENTORING SESSIONS. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY DID NOT GET A RESPONSE. HENCE, THE START-UP A DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

THE START-UP B PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (15/01/2024 & 29/01/2024) AND WORKED ON ALL SECTIONS OF THE BUSINESS PLAN PROVIDED BY CORALLIA. DISCUSSIONS FOCUSED ON FEEDBACK AND COMMENTS RELATED TO THE PRODUCED OUTCOME.

RESULTS

THE START-UP C PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (08/01/2024 & 22/01/2024) AND WORKED ON ALL SECTIONS OF THE BUSINESS PLAN PROVIDED BY CORALLIA. DISCUSSIONS FOCUSED ON FEEDBACK AND COMMENTS RELATED TO THE PRODUCED OUTCOME.

THE START-UP D COMMUNICATED THAT THEY HAD ISSUES TO ATTEND THE MENTORING SESSIONS. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY THE START-UP DECIDED TO NOT COMPLETE THIS MENTORING MODULE. HENCE, THE START-UP D DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H

REFLECTION SESSIONS

STRUCTURE

A ONE-HOUR REFLECTION SESSION WAS OFFERED TO ALL MENTEES ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THIS SESSION FOCUSED ON PROVIDING FEEDBACK TO THE MENTEES AND MARKED THE END OF THIS MENTORING MODULE

GOAL

THE REFLECTION SESSION AIMS TO ENCOURAGE PARTICIPANTS TO PRACTICE SELF-ASSESSMENT AND REFLECTION, ENABLING THEM TO MONITOR THEIR PROGRESS, ACKNOWLEDGE THEIR ACHIEVEMENTS, AND IDENTIFY AREAS FOR FUTURE DEVELOPMENT.

CONTENT	<p>IN THE REFLECTION SESSION, A GUIDED DISCUSSION BETWEEN THE MENTOR AND THE MENTEE TOOK PLACE. THE FOCUS WAS PUT ON REVIEWING THE BUSINESS PLAN AND DEVELOPING ACTIONS TO IMPROVE THE START-UP IN THE FUTURE.</p> <p>THE START-UP B PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION (19/02/2024) AND THE FINALIZED RESULT OF THE START-UP WAS EVALUATED AND THE LAST FEEDBACK WAS PROVIDED. A PLAN WAS SET FOR THE PRIORITIZED FUTURE STEPS THAT THE TEAM SHOULD FOLLOW TO ACTIVATE THEIR BUSINESS PLAN.</p>
RESULTS	<p>THE START-UP C PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION (12/02/2024) AND THE FINALIZED RESULT OF THE START-UP WAS EVALUATED AND THE LAST FEEDBACK WAS PROVIDED. A PLAN WAS SET FOR THE PRIORITIZED FUTURE STEPS THAT THE TEAM SHOULD FOLLOW TO ACTIVATE THEIR BUSINESS PLAN.</p> <p>TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H</p>

4.6 CLEANTECH BULGARIA - ACCESS TO FINANCE AND RELATED FUNDING

TRAINING VIDEOS

STRUCTURE	<p>THE TRAINING VIDEOS SERVE AS THE INITIAL MENTORING ELEMENT, WITH EACH OF THE THREE VIDEOS LASTING ABOUT ONE HOUR, A TOTAL OF APPROXIMATELY THREE HOURS OF VIDEO MATERIAL IS PROVIDED. THE MENTORS PRE-RECORD THE VIDEOS, WHICH ARE THEN LINKED TO ON THE F6S PLATFORM.</p>
GOAL	<p>THE TRAINING VIDEOS AIM TO INTRODUCE THE MENTEES INTO THE TOPIC OF THE MODULE AND PROVIDE THEM WITH A BASIC UNDERSTANDING OF THE ESSENTIAL COMPONENTS OF THE MODULE. THE FIRST VIDEO SERVES AS AN INTRODUCTORY SESSION TO THE TOPIC OF THE MENTORING MODULE. THE SECOND VIDEO DELVES DEEPER INTO THE MODULE'S TOPICS, WHILE THE FINAL VIDEO FOCUSES ON THE MOST COMPLEX ASPECTS COVERED IN THE MENTORING MODULE.</p> <p>VIDEO 1: IN THIS INTRODUCTORY VIDEO, PARTICIPANTS EMBARK ON A JOURNEY TO GAIN A PROFOUND UNDERSTANDING OF THE MULTIFACETED FUNDING LANDSCAPE AVAILABLE FOR STARTUPS. DELVING INTO VARIOUS FINANCING OPTIONS, INCLUDING CROWDFUNDING, GRANTS, LOANS, ANGEL INVESTMENTS, VENTURE CAPITAL, AND BOOTSTRAPPING, THE VIDEO METICULOUSLY EXPLORES THE IMPLICATIONS, ADVANTAGES, AND DRAWBACKS OF EACH FUNDING AVENUE. THE ULTIMATE OBJECTIVE IS TO EQUIP THE ENTREPRENEURS WITH THE KNOWLEDGE NEEDED TO IDENTIFY AND DIFFERENTIATE FUNDING OPTIONS TAILORED TO DIFFERENT STAGES OF THEIR STARTUP'S LIFECYCLE. THIS FOUNDATIONAL KNOWLEDGE SETS THE STAGE FOR THEIR VENTURE INTO THE DYNAMIC REALM OF STARTUP FUNDING.</p>
CONTENT	<p>VIDEO 2: THIS VIDEO GUIDES THE PARTICIPANTS THROUGH THE PROCESS OF ACCURATELY ASSESSING THE FINANCIAL NEEDS OF THEIR STARTUPS. OVER THE COURSE OF THE SESSION, PARTICIPANTS DELVE INTO KEY ASPECTS OF FINANCIAL PLANNING ESSENTIAL FOR STARTUP SUSTAINABILITY. THE VIDEO COVERS THE DEVELOPMENT OF A ROBUST FINANCIAL MODEL, FORECASTING REVENUE AND EXPENSES, AND DETERMINING CRITICAL CASH FLOW NEEDS. BY PROVIDING PRACTICAL TIPS ON CREATING REALISTIC AND CONVINCING FINANCIAL PROJECTIONS, PARTICIPANTS GAIN THE SKILLS NECESSARY TO NAVIGATE THE FINANCIAL INTRICACIES OF THEIR VENTURES. THE OVERARCHING GOAL IS TO EMPOWER PARTICIPANTS TO DEVELOP A COMPREHENSIVE UNDERSTANDING OF THEIR</p>

STARTUP'S FINANCIAL REQUIREMENTS, A PIVOTAL STEP TOWARD SECURING THE NECESSARY FUNDING FOR GROWTH.

RESULTS

ALL TRAINING VIDEOS HAVE BEEN PROVIDED BY THE MENTORING ORGANIZATION AND HAVE BEEN CONSUMED BY THE MENTEES.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H

QUIZ

STRUCTURE

ON THE F6S PLATFORM, A MULTIPLE-CHOICE QUIZ WAS IMPLEMENTED FOR EVERY MENTORING MODULE. THE AMOUNT OF QUESTIONS RANGED BETWEEN 24 AND 30. THE QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE THREE MENTORING VIDEOS. IT WAS ESTIMATED THAT THE COMPLETION OF ONE QUIZ TAKES ONE HOUR.

GOAL

THE QUIZ IS NON-MANDATORY BUT AIMS TO TEST THE MENTEES UNDERSTANDING OF MENTORING VIDEOS TO THEN FOCUS IN THE FOLLOWING MENTORING PROCESS ON AREAS WHERE THE PERFORMANCE IN THE QUIZ WAS LACKING.

CONTENT

THE QUIZ INCLUDES BOTH THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE CONTENT PRESENTED IN THE 2 VIDEOS OF THE MODULE. THE QUESTIONS ARE FORMED IN A WAY THAT MAKES IT EASY TO VERIFY WHETHER THE MENTEES HAVE INDEED WATCHED THE VIDEOS, AND TO IDENTIFY SPECIFIC AREAS ON WHICH THE TEAMS MAY NEED EXTRA CLARIFICATIONS.

RESULTS

UNFORTUNATELY, NONE OF THE TEAMS COMPLETED THE QUIZ.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

WORKSHOP

STRUCTURE

THE WORKSHOP SESSION IS THE FIRST LIVE INTERACTION OF THE MENTOR AND THE MENTEES. THE SESSION IS HELD ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THE WORKSHOP SESSION HAS A DURATION OF 2 HOURS AND IS OPEN FOR ALL MENTEES.

GOAL

IN THE WORKSHOP THE DIFFERENT MENTEES CAN APPLY THE THEORETICAL CONCEPTS LEARNED IN THE TRAINING VIDEOS TO THEIR OWN BUSINESS ENDEAVOR.

CONTENT

THE WORKSHOP FOCUSED ON PROVIDING THE MENTEES WITH AN IN-DEPTH UNDERSTANDING OF FUNDING OPPORTUNITIES AT THEIR CURRENT DEVELOPMENT LEVEL.

ALL FOUR TEAMS PARTICIPATED IN THE WORKSHOP AND UNDERSTOOD ITS CONTENT.

RESULTS

THE WORKSHOP HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON 23/11/2023.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H

Q&A SESSION

STRUCTURE

THE Q&A SESSION WAS FACILITATED ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THE DURATION OF THE SESSION WAS 1 HOUR AND OPEN FOR ALL MENTEES TO ENTER AND ASK QUESTIONS ABOUT MENTORING RELATED TOPICS.

GOAL

THE Q&A SESSION AIMS TO PROVIDE THE MENTEES WITH AN OPPORTUNITY TO ASK QUESTIONS AND TO SOLVE DOUBTS RAISED FROM THE PREVIOUS TRAINING VIDEOS AND WORKSHOP.

CONTENT

THE Q&A WAS SPLIT TO TWO SESSIONS FOR THE CONVENIENCE OF THE PARTICIPATING TEAMS. THERE GENERAL TOPICS WERE DISCUSSED.

RESULTS

ONLY THE TEAMS B AND C PARTICIPATED IN THE Q&A SESSION. THEY INFORMED THE MENTOR THAT DUE TO EXTERNAL CIRCUMSTANCES THEY WERE NOT ABLE TO KEEP UP WITH THE CONTENT OF THE MENTORING MODULE AND WOULD LIKE TO POSTPONE THE UPCOMING INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS BY A BIT. THIS POINT OF VIEW WAS SHARED BY CLEANTECH, AND IT WAS DECIDED TO RESCHEDULE THE UPCOMING INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS.

THE SESSIONS HAVE BEEN CONDUCTED ON 15/12/2023.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS

STRUCTURE

TWO INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS FOR EACH START-UP, EACH WITH A DURATION OF ONE HOUR, WERE OFFERED ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR, LEADING TO A TOTAL OF TWO HOURS OF MENTORING PER START-UP. IN THESE SESSIONS ONLY, THE MENTORS AND ONE START-UP ARE PRESENT TO FOCUS ON THEIR SPECIFIC NEEDS AND ISSUES.

GOAL

THE INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS PROVIDE PERSONALIZED GUIDANCE TO EACH START-UP, HELPING THEM OVERCOME SPECIFIC OBSTACLES ENCOUNTERED DURING CRITICAL PHASES OF THEIR COMPANIES. THIS ASSISTANCE AIDS IN DEVELOPING EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR THE FUTURE.

CONTENT

DURING THE INDIVIDUAL SESSION, THE MENTOR ADDRESSES SPECIFIC NEEDS OF THE MENTEE RELATED TO THE MODULE. THIS CAN RANGE FROM IDENTIFYING SUITABLE FUNDING OPPORTUNITIES TO APPROACHING POTENTIAL INVESTORS

RESULTS

THE START-UP A COMMUNICATED THAT THEY HAD ISSUES TO ATTEND THE MENTORING SESSIONS. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY DID NOT GET A RESPONSE. HENCE, THE START-UP A DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

THE START-UP B PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS BMC (13/02/2024 & 20/02/2024). THROUGHOUT THE DURATION OF THE SESSIONS, SUITABLE OPPORTUNITIES FOR FUNDING (SUCH AS GRANTS, INVESTMENTS, AND PARTICIPATION IN OTHER PROGRAMS) WERE EXPLORED. FURTHER, THE MENTEES THEIR MAIN INTEREST WAS ON

INVESTORS, SO PLATFORMS WITH ADDITIONAL LEARNING RESOURCES AND MASTERCLASSES ON THE INVESTOR'S MINDSET AND APPROACH WERE EXPLORED

THE START-UP C PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (09/02/2024 & 16/02/2024). THE MENTEE EXPRESSED A MAIN INTEREST IN OPPORTUNITIES FOR OBTAINING FUNDING. AS A RESULT, THE SESSIONS WERE FOCUSED ON EXPLORING PLATFORMS (SUCH AS F6S AND LOCAL OPPORTUNITIES) AND PROGRAMS (INCLUDING HORIZON EUROPE, EIT, EIC, AND LOCAL OPPORTUNITIES). MULTIPLE PROGRAMS FOR THE CONTINUATION OF THE MOMENTUM THEY OBTAINED DURING THEIR PARTICIPATION IN THE ENTREPRENEDEDU PROGRAM WERE IDENTIFIED. GOALS WERE SET, AND C AIMED TO APPLY TO AT LEAST ONE NEW PROGRAM FOR ADDITIONAL COACHING AND FUNDING OF THEIR PROJECT

THE START-UP D COMMUNICATED THAT THEY HAD ISSUES TO ATTEND THE MENTORING SESSIONS. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY THE START-UP DECIDED TO NOT COMPLETE THIS MENTORING MODULE. HENCE, THE START-UP D DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H

REFLECTION SESSIONS

STRUCTURE	A ONE-HOUR REFLECTION SESSION WAS OFFERED TO ALL MENTEES ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THIS SESSION FOCUSED ON PROVIDING FEEDBACK TO THE MENTEES AND MARKED THE END OF THIS MENTORING MODULE
GOAL	THE REFLECTION SESSION AIMS TO ENCOURAGE PARTICIPANTS TO PRACTICE SELF-ASSESSMENT AND REFLECTION, ENABLING THEM TO MONITOR THEIR PROGRESS, ACKNOWLEDGE THEIR ACHIEVEMENTS, AND IDENTIFY AREAS FOR FUTURE DEVELOPMENT.
CONTENT	THE SESSION SERVED AS A DISCUSSION GROUND FOR ALL REMAINING QUESTIONS FROM THE MENTEE ABOUT FUNDING OPPORTUNITIES AND REFLECTION ON THE EXPERIENCE THROUGHOUT THE PROGRAM.
RESULTS	THE REFLECTION SESSION OF TEAM B TOOK PLACE ON 27/02/2024 AND OF TEAM C ON 01/03/2024. FEEDBACK ON THE INVOLVEMENT OF THE TEAM AS WELL AS ON THE PERFORMANCE AND GUIDANCE FROM THE MENTOR WAS EXCHANGED. THE TEAMS SHARED THAT THEY FOUND THE PROGRAM VERY USEFUL AND THE MENTORS WERE VERY WELL PREPARED AND PROVIDED RELEVANT INFORMATION. BOTH TEAMS EXPRESSED WILLINGNESS TO SHARE THEIR TESTIMONIALS DURING THE INFO WEBINAR ORGANIZED FOR THE 3RD HACKTHEBUSINESS EVENT IN ORDER TO MOTIVATE NEW STUDENTS TO TAKE THIS JOURNEY.
	TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

4.7 FEEDBACK OF THE MENTEES

As part of the project's commitment to continuous improvement and to ensure the program's alignment with the evolving needs of entrepreneurs, a comprehensive feedback collection process has been embarked upon the completion of the first cohort. This chapter is dedicated to presenting the insights

garnered from this feedback, which is instrumental in refining and enhancing the program for subsequent cohorts.

The feedback collected from the participants serves as a cornerstone for the understanding of the program's impact, effectiveness, and areas requiring enhancement. Through a designed feedback guideline, the participants' experiences, challenges faced, and the learning outcomes achieved throughout their mentoring journey has been collected. The feedback guideline was structured to explore various dimensions of the program, including the skills and knowledge they acquired, their progress and goal setting, their interaction with the mentorship community, and their overall satisfaction with the program organisation.

This chapter aims to elucidate the methodology behind the feedback collection, summarize the key findings, and outline the measures we plan to implement to improve future iterations of the ENTREPRENEDU mentoring program.

4.7.1 METHODOLOGY FOR FEEDBACK COLLECTION

The feedback collection for the ENTREPRENEDU mentoring program's first cohort was conducted with a qualitative approach to collect the participants' experiences. This process was designed and executed by two researchers from Fraunhofer, the partner responsible for the development and coordination of the mentoring program. It was gathered through guided online video calls. This approach allowed for a more dynamic and interactive exchange of information, providing clearer insights into the participants' experiences, perceptions, and suggestions for improvement. The methodology was structured around a semi-structured feedback guideline, exploring the following eight sections:

Section 1 - Reflection on the Mentoring Journey: Participants were asked to articulate their start-up's initial vision and how their objectives evolved, providing insights into the mentoring program's transformative impact. The guiding questions were:

- *Describe the initial vision and objectives for your start-up/team. How have these evolved over the course of the program?*
- *Reflect on the inception of your future business. What were the key assumptions, and how have they been validated or revised?*

Section 2 - Overcoming Obstacles and Developing Skills: This section delved into the significant obstacles participants faced and the skills they developed, highlighting the program's role in equipping them with necessary entrepreneurial competencies. The guiding questions were:

- *Identify the most significant challenges you faced while developing your start-up/team. How did you overcome these obstacles?*
- *Reflect on the skills and knowledge you have developed during the mentoring program. Which of these do you consider most valuable for your future growth?*
- *How did the mentoring sessions and interactions with peers contribute to your journey? Provide examples of insights gained or changes implemented as a result.*

Section 3 - Business Model Evaluation: Participants evaluated their developed business model's effectiveness, discussing strengths, areas for improvement, and their competitive positioning in the market. The guiding questions were:

- *Assess the effectiveness of your developed business model. What are its strengths, and where does it need improvement?*
- *How does your business address the needs of your target market? Discuss any feedback received from potential customers or stakeholders and how it has shaped your approach.*
- *Considering the competitive landscape, how does your start-up/team differentiate itself? Is there a unique value proposition or innovation that sets you apart?*

Section 4 - Progress and Future Goals: Reflecting on their growth and future aspirations, participants were asked to share the success metrics they use, their goals, and how the program has prepared them for upcoming entrepreneurial challenges. The guiding questions were:

- *How do you measure the success and impact of your start-up/team? Discuss any metrics or indicators you use to track progress.*
- *What are the short-term and long-term goals for your start-up/team? Outline the steps you plan to take to achieve these goals.*
- *Reflecting on the ENTREPRENEDU program, how has it prepared you for the next stages of your entrepreneurial journey? Identify any gaps or additional support you may need moving forward.*

Section 5 - Learning from the Community: Insights were gathered on the advice and knowledge exchanged within the community, analysing the program's collaborative learning environment. The guiding questions were:

- *Share a key learning or piece of advice you received from another participant or mentor that has impacted your start-up/team strategy.*
- *How do you envision contributing to the ENTREPRENEDU community and the wider entrepreneurial ecosystem in the future?*

Section 6 - Overall Satisfaction with the Mentoring Program and Modules: The section sought participants' overall impressions of the program and specific modules, gathering detailed feedback on what was most valuable and identifying areas for enhancement. The guiding questions were:

- *How satisfied are you with the overall ENTREPRENEDU mentoring program?*
- *For each of the following modules, please rate your satisfaction on a scale of 1 to 5 (1 is not satisfied at all and 5 is extremely satisfied) and provide specific feedback on what you found valuable and areas for improvement.*
- *What aspects of the program did you find most valuable? Please explain.*
- *Were there any areas of the program you feel could be improved? Please provide specific suggestions.*

Section 7 - Technical and Organisational Feedback: Participants were asked about the technical and organisational aspects of the programme, such as the technical implementation in the platform as well as the scheduling process. The guiding questions were:

- *How well did the mentoring modules integrate with one another to provide a cohesive learning experience?*
- *How do you assess the technical implementation of the ENTREPRENEDU mentoring program?*
- *How easy was it for you to schedule appointments with your mentors?*
- *Are there any additional topics or areas you wish were covered in the mentoring program?*

Section 8 - Closing thoughts: The participants were asked if there are any other thoughts or reflections they would like to share that have not been covered by the previous questions. The guiding question was:

- *Are there any other thoughts or reflections you would like to share that have not been covered in this questionnaire?*

The feedback sessions were scheduled and conducted in February 2024, immediately following the conclusion of the first cohort, in conjunction with the reflection sessions of the module business model development led by Fraunhofer IPK. Each team was invited to a one-on-one online video call, which allowed for a personal and in-depth exploration of their experiences. The sessions were not only aimed at gathering structured feedback, but also at understanding the subtleties of each participant's entrepreneurial journey within the program. The qualitative data collected through these sessions were then analyzed by the researchers to identify common themes, insights, and areas of improvement. This analysis was instrumental in developing targeted recommendations for enhancing the ENTREPRENEDU mentoring program for future cohorts.

4.7.2 PRESENTATION OF FEEDBACK RESULTS

This chapter distils the feedback across key areas of the program, encapsulating the entrepreneurial journey's essence as experienced by the participants.

Section 1 - Reflection on the Mentoring Journey

Participants reported a development of their business ideas and models, highlighting the program's effectiveness in steering their ideas towards greater feasibility and concrete business planning. The mentoring journey was described as transformative, with mentors playing a crucial role in challenging assumptions, offering guidance, and enabling the teams to refine their visions into more concrete businesses. This evolution was not just about the ideas themselves, but also about participants' mindsets towards a more strategic, market-oriented approach.

Section 2 - Overcoming Obstacles and Developing Skills

The feedback highlighted a variety of challenges faced by the teams, ranging from concerns about scalability to the complexities of integrating the learned modules into their strategic business planning effectively. The program played an important role in enabling participants to surmount these hurdles by

providing focused support to cultivate essential skills such as problem validation, value proposition creation, and proficient pitch delivery. These competencies were indispensable not only for the immediate refinement of their business ideas but also for growth in a competitive market environment. Nonetheless, one team, which was at the nascent stage of idea development upon entering the program, expressed that it was challenging to grasp the interplay among the different modules and the sequence in which to apply them. They found it difficult to discern which video lesson to prioritize and how to systematically incorporate all the videos from the different modules in the correct sequence.

Section 3 - Business Model Evaluation

The teams identified specific needs for further improvement in their revenue streams, market awareness, and competitive differentiation. Through the mentoring process, value propositions were clarified and strengthened, enabling the teams to better position themselves in the market. The iterative feedback and validation process within the program were highlighted as instrumental in refining these business model components, demonstrating the value of continuous mentorship and peer review.

Section 4 - Progress and Future Goals

Participants expressed appreciation for the program's effectiveness in assisting them with establishing actionable short-term and long-term goals, as well as metrics for gauging their success. The feedback highlighted the critical nature of setting clear, measurable objectives and affirmed the program's capability in readying teams for subsequent phases of their entrepreneurial journey. Nonetheless, the feedback also pinpointed gaps, particularly in the need for additional support in actualizing these plans, signalling a requirement for enhanced mentorship or resources in specific domains. Within this framework, one team identified a need for further assistance in securing grants or funding to realize their business idea. Additional expertise in specific areas, such as technological feasibility, was deemed beneficial to fortify confidence in certain aspects of their business model. Moreover, there was a recognized necessity for guidance in forming a robust team, including strategies related to human resources.

Section 5 - Learning from the Community

The invaluable role of mentors was consistently highlighted in the feedback, with their insights, advice, and support significantly enhancing the learning experience. This exchange cultivated a collaborative learning environment that participants greatly appreciated. When considering peer-to-peer learning, the feedback presented a dichotomy. While some participants were highly satisfied with the opportunity to engage with other teams and expressed a desire for more structured interaction opportunities, others noted that, due to diverse business backgrounds, their engagement was more fruitful with mentors than with peers. Additionally, one team suggested spacing out the sessions for the various modules over a longer period. This approach would not extend the program's overall duration but would allow for a more distributed and in-depth exploration of each module, offering participants additional time to absorb, implement, and reflect on the learnings between sessions.

Section 6 - Overall Satisfaction with the Mentoring Program and Modules

The overall satisfaction with the ENTREPRENUEDU mentoring program, as reported by the participating teams, reflects a high level of satisfaction across the various modules, with most ratings being very

satisfied (5 out of 5). A summary of the collective feedback and satisfaction ratings for each module is presented as follows:

Module 1: Business Model Development

Participants found significant value in the assistance provided to complete the business model canvas, highlighting the competence and availability of mentors. The guidance on effectively filling out the canvas was particularly appreciated, although there was feedback that the mentor's involvement sometimes made it challenging for participants to internalize the solutions independently.

Module 2: Crafting a Unique and Competitive Value Proposition

This module was highlighted as especially stimulating, with its interactive nature and practical tasks awakening a crucial understanding of value proposition among entrepreneurs. Participants suggested that idea validation, a core component of this module, would be more beneficial if placed at the very beginning of the program.

Module 3: Your Idea Pitch: from Tech Feasibility to Product Development

The module was highly appreciated, highlighting the strong competence of the mentors, accompanied by a suggestion to separate the tech feasibility aspect from the idea pitch, as not all participants had a product already developed. It was proposed that the structuring of this module should consider the participants' readiness level more closely. Additionally, the recommendation to include technical guidance for product development was made to further enrich this module.

Module 4: Investment Pitch and Quantifying Your Funding Needs

The investment pitch module was very well-regarded, and participants highlighted especially the very precise and personalized feedback they received. However, it also highlighted a need for more foundational knowledge for some participants.

Module 5: Entrepreneurial Business Planning

The business planning module was praised for its interactivity and the extensive input provided. Participants appreciated the opportunity for discussions and the engaging approach of the module, which stimulated significant thought and reflection on their business planning.

Module 6: Access to Finance and Related Funding

Feedback for this module underscored its straightforward and concrete approach to addressing finance and funding, with adaptations made to fit the situation of the participants. The practical focus of this module was particularly valued.

Section 7: Technical and Organisational Feedback

Teams acknowledged the mentoring modules' role in providing a cohesive learning experience, though they suggested improvements for better integration. The sequence of modules, particularly the placement of problem validation early in the program, was noted as an area for improvement. Feedback indicated that an early focus on problem validation could lead to more meaningful shifts in business ideas, suggesting a need for clearer guidance on how different modules interact and complement each other.

The technical aspect of the program was generally well-received, with the platform described as satisfactory and the process for accessing materials like videos being straightforward.

Scheduling appointments emerged as a significant challenge, primarily due to the use of multiple emails and channels, which led to confusion and scheduling difficulties. The feedback strongly suggests the need for a unified scheduling process to streamline communication and make it easier for participants to manage their interactions with mentors, especially considering the constraints of participants' work schedules.

While not all teams specified unaddressed areas, there was a clear call for the inclusion of topics related to HR Management and Leadership. Specifically, guidance on hiring and managing a team was identified as a critical area for additional content, underscoring the need for entrepreneurial leadership skills alongside the program's existing focus areas.

4.7.3 SUMMARY OF DERIVED MEASURES AND IMPROVEMENTS

Based on the insightful feedback collected from the inaugural cohort of the ENTREPRENUEDU mentoring program, several key areas for enhancement have been identified. Based on the feedback, recommendations for improvement have been derived:

TABLE 2: Summary of Improvements for the ENTREPRENUEDU Mentoring Programme

ENHANCEMENTS TO THE MENTORING JOURNEY	
STRUCTURED INTEGRATION OF MODULES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DEVELOP CLEARER GUIDELINES ON THE SEQUENCE AND INTERPLAY OF DIFFERENT MODULES TO AID PARTICIPANTS IN EFFECTIVELY INCORPORATING LEARNED CONCEPTS INTO THEIR BUSINESS PLANNING. PRIORITIZE PROBLEM VALIDATION AT THE PROGRAM'S OUTSET TO ENCOURAGE IMMEDIATE AND IMPACTFUL IDEATIONAL SHIFTS.
INCREASED MENTOR ENGAGEMENT IN IDEA DEVELOPMENT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FOSTER A BALANCE BETWEEN MENTOR INVOLVEMENT AND PARTICIPANT AUTONOMY IN THE BUSINESS MODEL DEVELOPMENT PROCESS TO ENSURE PARTICIPANTS INTERNALIZE SOLUTIONS INDEPENDENTLY WHILE BENEFITING FROM EXPERT GUIDANCE.
SKILL DEVELOPMENT AND BUSINESS EVALUATION	
MODULAR READINESS ADAPTATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TAILOR MODULES SUCH AS "YOUR IDEA PITCH: FROM TECH FEASIBILITY TO PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT" TO PARTICIPANTS' READINESS LEVELS, PARTICULARLY DISTINGUISHING BETWEEN THOSE WITH AND WITHOUT DEVELOPED PRODUCTS. INCORPORATE

	<p>TECHNICAL GUIDANCE FOR PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT AS AN INTEGRAL COMPONENT OF RELEVANT MODULES.</p>
FOUNDATION KNOWLEDGE ENHANCEMENT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IN MODULES LIKE THE "INVESTMENT PITCH AND QUANTIFYING YOUR FUNDING NEEDS" INCORPORATE MORE FOUNDATIONAL KNOWLEDGE CONTENT TO ENSURE ALL PARTICIPANTS, REGARDLESS OF THEIR STARTING POINT, CAN FULLY ENGAGE WITH AND BENEFIT FROM THE SESSIONS.
PROGRAM STRUCTURE AND DELIVERY	
EXTENDED MODULE DURATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WITHOUT PROLONGING THE PROGRAM'S OVERALL DURATION, EXTEND THE SPACING BETWEEN SESSIONS TO ALLOW DEEPER ABSORPTION AND REFLECTION OF THE CONTENT. THIS PACING WOULD ENABLE PARTICIPANTS TO APPLY LEARNINGS MORE EFFECTIVELY BETWEEN SESSIONS.
UNIFIED SCHEDULING SYSTEM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IMPLEMENT A STREAMLINED, UNIFIED SCHEDULING PROCESS TO REDUCE CONFUSION AND ENHANCE THE EASE OF ARRANGING MENTORSHIP APPOINTMENTS, ACCOMMODATING THE DIVERSE SCHEDULES OF PARTICIPANTS.
CURRICULAR EXPANSION	
INCLUSION OF LEADERSHIP AND HR MANAGEMENT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EXPAND THE CURRICULUM TO INCLUDE MODULES ON HR MANAGEMENT AND LEADERSHIP, PROVIDING VITAL SKILLS IN TEAM FORMATION AND MANAGEMENT, CRUCIAL FOR THE GROWTH AND SCALABILITY OF START-UP VENTURES.
TECHNICAL AND ORGANIZATIONAL FEEDBACK IMPLEMENTATION	
PLATFORM AND ACCESS IMPROVEMENTS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WHILE THE TECHNICAL PLATFORM WAS GENERALLY SATISFACTORY, EXPLORE OPPORTUNITIES TO ENHANCE USER INTERACTION AND EASE OF ACCESSING MATERIALS, ENSURING A SEAMLESS LEARNING EXPERIENCE.
COHESIVE LEARNING EXPERIENCE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ADDRESS FEEDBACK ON MODULE COHESION AND INTEGRATION THROUGH IMPROVED PROGRAM DESIGN, ENSURING A LOGICAL FLOW AND SYNERGY BETWEEN ALL COMPONENTS OF THE ENTREPRENEURIAL LEARNING JOURNEY.

By implementing these measures and addressing the areas for improvement, future mentoring cohorts can be even more successful in engaging participants, fostering collaboration, and achieving positive outcomes for all stakeholders involved.

5 OUTLOOK COHORT 2

The second Cohort comprises initially four teams selected from the Greek Hackathon held in Athens on November 25, 2023. Additionally, one team from the previous Hackathon in Rimini, Italy was included to give them the opportunity to complete the mentoring programme that they were unable to complete in the cohort 1 timeframe and to achieve the KPI of 12 fully participating teams in the mentoring programme, with the Italian team consisting of former members of the start-up D. The Kick-off meeting for the second cohort convened on January 23, 2024, with all Greek teams in attendance. Scheduled from January 2024 to April 2024, the second initiation follows the structure and content of the first cohort's schedule, with some adjustments based on feedback from Cohort 1. Notably, live sessions have been prioritized, and the consortium has opted to facilitate all live mentoring sessions through a single web application for consistency. Google Meets was selected as the preferred platform due to its ability to accommodate multiple simultaneous sessions. Shortly after the Kick-off meeting, the participating teams of Cohort 2 received the consortium's proposed schedule for the live sessions. Following the confirmation of final dates, Fraunhofer IPK extended invitations to the teams and mentors via Google Meets for their respective session. During the Kick-Off meeting it was emphasized that the completion of the quizzes is an integral part of the programme which resulted in a higher completion rate of the quizzes. Currently, phase 1 of the mentoring programme for Cohort 2 has been completed and sessions scheduled for phase 2 are taking place.

6 CONCLUSION

This report details the creation, structure, execution, and outcomes of the inaugural ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring Programme, alongside actions derived from participant feedback. The programme, featuring six modules integrating e-learning and interactive mentorship, aimed to provide a comprehensive journey for entrepreneurial teams from ideation to execution. The execution involved three phases, with the first two focussing on methodical preparation and development, culminating in reflection sessions where feedback was collected and measures for improvement were identified. While participants expressed high satisfaction, suggestions for enhancement were outlined, including clearer module guidelines and an expanded curriculum content. The report also provides insights into the ongoing mentoring process for Cohort 2, emphasizing adjustments made based on feedback from Cohort 1. With live sessions facilitated through Google Meets, Cohort 2 continues to follow the structure and objectives established in the first initiation. Further, the consortium decided to provide certifications for participants who successfully completed all aspects of the programme. This measure aims to increase the commitment and motivation of the participants, especially in the area of quiz completion. Ultimately, this report contributes to the ongoing efforts of the ENTREPRENEDU Project to bridge innovation and educational disparities across the EU.

7 APPENDIX

MENTORING PROGRAM SCHEDULE

GROUP SESSIONS (with all four teams)

Workshop Sessions (2 hour each)

Partner	Preferred Option (PF)	Name(s) of participating Mentors
Fraunhofer IPK	01.12.2023, 09.00-11.00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	22.11.2023, 10.00-12.00 CET	Paola Belingheri
FEA	21.11.2023, 10.00-12.00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	28.11.2023, 2.00-4.00pm CET	Jaak Ennuste
Corallia	29.11.2023, 1.00-3.00pm CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	23.11.2023, 2.00-4.00pm CET	Ina Todorova

Q&A Sessions (1 hour each)

Partner	Preferred Option (PF)	Name(s) of participating Mentors
Fraunhofer IPK	04.12.2023, 08.00-09.00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	06.12.2023, 10.00-11.00 CET	Paola Belingheri
FEA	12.12.2023, 10.00-11.00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	16.01.2023, 16.00-17.00 CET	Jaak Ennuste
Corallia	15.12.2023, 15.00-16.00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	15.12.2023, 14.00-15.00 CET	Ina Todorova

INDIVIDUAL TEAM SESSIONS

Team A

Mentoring Sessions

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	Did not participate	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	Did not participate	Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	Did not participate	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	Did not participate	Jaak Ennuste
Corallia	Did not participate	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	Did not participate	Ina Todorova

Partner	Session 2	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 2
Fraunhofer IPK	Did not participate	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	Did not participate	Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	Did not participate	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	Did not participate	Jaak Ennuste
Corallia	Did not participate	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	Did not participate	Ina Todorova

Reflection Session

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Reflection Session
Fraunhofer IPK	Did not participate	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	Did not participate	Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	Did not participate	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	Did not participate	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	Did not participate	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	Did not participate	Ina Todorova

Team B
Mentoring Sessions

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	08.01.2024, 08.00-09.00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	15.01.2024, 09:00-10:00 CET	Paola Belingheri
FEA	17.01.2024, 17.00-18.00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	13.02.2024, 12.00-13.00 CET	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	15.01.2024, 15:30-16:30 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	13.02.2024, 10:00-11:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Partner	Session 2	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 2
Fraunhofer IPK	22.01.2024, 08.00-09.00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	22.01.2024, 09:00-10:00 CET	Paola Belingheri
FEA	24.01.2024, 17.00-18.00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	19.02.2024, 11.30-12.30 CET	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	29.01.2024, 13:00-14:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	20.02.2024, 10:00-11:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Reflection Session

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Reflection Session
Fraunhofer IPK	12.02.2024, 08.00-09.00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	13.02.2024, 09:00-10:00 CET	Paola Belingheri
FEA	21.02.2024, 10.00-11.00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	19.03.2024, 10.30-11.30 CET	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	19.02.2024, 14:00-15:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	27.02.2024 10:00-11:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Team C
Mentoring Sessions

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	16.01.2024, 09.00-10.00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	10.01.2024, 12:00-13:00 CET	Paola Belingheri
FEA	16.01.2024, 17.00-18.00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	01.02.2024, 15.30-16.30 - CET	Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	08.01.2024, 10:00-11:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	09.02.2024, 11:00-12:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Partner	Session 2	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 2
Fraunhofer IPK	24.01.2024, 08.00-09.00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	22.01.2024, 12:00-13:00 CET	Paola Belingheri
FEA	23.01.2024, 17.00-18.00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	14.02.2024, 15.00-16.00 CET	Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	22.01.2024, 12:00-13:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	16.02.2024, 11:0 -12:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Reflection Session

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Reflection Session
Fraunhofer IPK	14.02.2024, 08.00-09.00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	05.02.2024, 12:00-13:00 CET	Paola Belingheri
FEA	19.02.2024, 10.00-11.00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	11.03.2024, 15.30-16.30 CET	Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	12.02.2024, 13:00-14:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	01.03.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Team D
Mentoring Sessions

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	15.01.2024, 08.00-09.00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	Did not participate	Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	Did not participate	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	Did not participate	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	Did not participate	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	Did not participate	Ina Todorova
Partner	Session 2	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 2
Fraunhofer IPK	01.02.2024, 08.00-09.00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	Did not participate	Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	Did not participate	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	Did not participate	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	Did not participate	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	Did not participate	Ina Todorova

Reflection Session

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Reflection Session
Fraunhofer IPK	16.02.2024, 08.00-09.00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	Did not participate	Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	Did not participate	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	Did not participate	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	Did not participate	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	Did not participate	Ina Todorova